

Using Nyquist Plots from Nonlinear Control Theory to Understand the Riemann Zeta Function Zeros

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Abstract: First we research the rudiments of circuits, control theory and general research in electrical engineering and physics and then the details of a single experiment is gone over: a magnetic levitation experiment. The magnetic levitation apparatus built as well as the circuit, software and hardware is gone into as well as the theory for the physics of this device and the mathematical model as well as the circuit model. Plots for the zeta function are given as well as magnitude and phasor plots of the zeta function. Nyquist plots are done for the magnetic levitator experiment from the magnetic levitator transfer function and then lastly the Nyquist plots are performed on the zeta function.

Introduction:

Transfer Functions [1], [1.1] encode the important information of circuit variables and the mathematical methodology known as Frequency Response [2] -which is used to understand the physical happenings of the circuit- is closely related to topics in Number Theory [3] such as the Riemann Zeta Function [4] through the lens of abstraction. These topics are also very closely related to mathematics involved with the differential geometry [5] necessary for physically realizable field theories such as Electrodynamics [6] and General Relativity [7], and this report briefly discusses this relation. This paper is separated into two main parts: the mathematical part discussing the zeta function and systems part, depicts the rudimentary properties of the levitation system as shown from oscilloscope [8] and hall effect sensor data [9]. A simulation of the Riemann Zeta Transfer Function [10] simultaneously as the primed Riemann Zeta Transfer Function with semi logarithmic scaling shows that the stability conditions [11] which are analogous to the definitions of zero are met only at the critical line. This same method is used to analyze the circuit [12] which is a magnetic levitation system [13]. Magnetic levitation systems are nonlinear systems [14] because the electromagnetic field created from the current going through them is nonlinear. By looking at the evolution of the stability conditions in time and over the variation of a resistance parameter of a levitation system, the same method of analysis which implicates the zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function to be at the critical line due to the relationship of the definition of stability and symmetry with the analogy is used to show how the Nyquist plot [15] for the circuit in a magnetic levitation experiment changes over the variation. The result of the method mainly is that functions, such as the RZTF and the RZTF' can be relatively compared using time simulations and although in this case, the RZTF' was used to prove the symmetry condition only being met at the critical line, arbitrary RZTF's can be constructed, so long as the properties are defined correctly.

It seems to me that Quantum Mechanics uses Complex Numbers and the General Theory of Relativity takes such definitions to be ill defined, although complex algebra occurs in solutions, and in the neighboring theory of electrodynamics in some cases, and that by some derivation of complex definitions, matter terms which are imaginary in some frames add energy to the system. After researching this and writing a book on this particular topic, the simple result arose: Geometrically speaking, Quantum Mechanical frames can be shown to require complex numbers to describe the bases, and so therefore in some respect, the definitions of particles and objects must be Complex in some respect. This fact does occur throughout Physics and engineering, as discussed in. From such considerations, one is almost immediately compelled to amuse the idea of complex definitions during the derivation of the field theory, where all of the terms, including the Energy are adjusted to try to compensate for the known discrepancy of Dark Matter [16] because any extended theory of Relativity should maintain true the simple fact that the Dark Matter must be relative to the ordinary matter from which the mathematical discrepancies are observed. A particle physics theory would arise from a proper definition of Complex Relativity because of the fact then the mechanism of relativity is prepared to handle the complex space times that will be acted on to construct what we perceive as material objects. Very simply put, Dark Matter most likely from the simple thought

experiments constructed has to be modeled with as a relativistic field effect, and although that is not the topic of this project, it previously was a driving force because, that if this is possible, then a general mechanism for describing any systems including circuit phenomena must be complex valued, which is currently the main practice in engineering circuit theory. One finds that in the more advanced topics, generally complex analysis is used as a tool, however, not usually within the definitions is the complex algebra used. The zeta function for example occurs in some solutions to some differential equations and it also occurs in statistical mechanics. So I thought complex analysis was the basis of this and it turns out that this is wrong and that although the model of dark matter I came up with had an intuitive description the mathematical derivation simply was not rigorous enough to make any real coherent predictions. But this is important it turns out for the unification of general relativity with quantum electrodynamics as quantum space times are inherently complex valued.

This led me to explore the rudiments of a large variety of differential equations for physical phenomena and ultimately to understand better, root and polynomial equations because of the fact that differential equations might easily be described as root equations. After trying virtually every undergraduate technique I knew, and creating an archive for the mathematical topic known as the Riemann Zeta Function, and reading many proofs of the facts, theorems, and operations which compose the RZF, I began to understand better what the problem statement was, and the definitions of all of the related functions and variables primarily by looking at definitions checking multiple references for those definitions, proofs and derivations of the functions. This took a lot of effort particularly because the field of study was related to other projects I had done, but not everything lined up and Complex Analysis itself was a topic entirely ignorant to me when I created the concept of the Cauchy-Riemann equations from complex operators, and explored proving the RH, but due to the fact that I had previously been very well researched in Calculus [17], Calculus of Variations [18], Multivariate Calculus [19], Tensor Calculus [20], Differential Geometry and General Relativity, the extension I created was through a method of analyzing mathematical problems that I created during my undergraduate experience at Cleveland State University and constantly thinking about the differential equations of the resulting analyses particularly in circuit theory (where the Laplace Transformation [21] method initially was tough to comprehend), whether it be a PDE [22] from an advanced analysis or an ordinary linear differential equation [23].

When Z. Gao, my professor for Signals and Systems at Cleveland State University (CSU) began talking about Nyquist -whom I knew nothing of- and what he had done, it occurred how deeply connected the material I had studied in my spare time with the RZF were to circuit theory, that I had apparently created material which is very similar to Nyquist's mathematical solution for circuit theory application, which did not shock me due to the fact that my previous professor for circuits, C. Alexander, discussed very thoroughly the complex connection to circuit theory, without Nyquist, and actually during the final exam in Circuits II, it dawned on me, precisely the issue I was having with finishing my first proof of the RH using an algorithm I created because I kept consistently achieving the same incorrect answers with a method I created for solving those particular circuit problems which went against the formal training in physics I was at the time receiving such as in Classical mechanics. Usually this is because I missed a minus sign or used the incorrect function to initialize the derivation. Much of my understanding of the Riemann Zeta Function has come from reading B. Riemann's Manuscript, the proofs of Euler, and the original work of many of the mathematicians and scientists who have produced useful technology and methodology, etc. In this paper, I will be graphing the RZF with Bode Plots, so to see the analogous circuit relations which are inherently related to the definitions of zero, specifically symmetry and stability [24]. The swapping of the Real and Imaginary components indicate this condition numerically, but in the simulation, it is the symmetry and direction of change of the graphs of the phase and magnitude plots. The Bode Plots [25] show that the RH is true because they show given the 3-D time parameterization how both the phase symmetry conditions and magnitude overlapping conditions are simultaneously met. A derivative map [26] could further be produced, or a 3-D Nyquist plot analogous to the Bode plot would show identically the same, specifically, that the stability criteria are met only at $x = 1/2$ given the parameterization method. This is true only because of the analogy of the symmetry conditions to the stability conditions for the Riemann Zeta Transfer Function which is

constructed with the RZF and a specific coordinate transformation of the RZF. But the plots are essentially useless because a finite proof of the Riemann Hypothesis does not prove the Riemann Hypothesis. The Nyquist plots do however give information about the stability of the RZTF and this is a numerical proof of the Riemann Hypothesis.

I began with a basic draft for a magnetic cannon [27] which was able to propel a magnetic material [28] due to the lectures and discussions with U. Zurcher [29] about the rudimentary physics operation of a rail gun [30], as such could be imagined for a simple linear DC machine [31] my teammates put together but ultimately realized that the mathematical model for the field controller could be used for a single force inducer to produce essentially all of these experiments. Similar experiments such as the single ring Thompson jumping ring experiment [32] performed by Z. Gao [33] are performed at CSU for showing students the operation of the Faraday-Lenz law [34]. It is sort of funny how the original drafts to show how the device which went from a simple image drawn at Denny's at 3 am in crayon to a way to test stability conditions in a nonlinear differential equation [35] using the Laplace transform can turn into a full blown research endeavor in the mathematical models of magnetic field control systems.

The laboratory for the power source and lectures with A. Stankovic have given me the opportunity to step down the voltage with a CT transformer [36] within the lab as well as a better understanding of generators, giving me a large range of power input to have although for the final design decided upon a large voltage is not needed, so that the control circuit which is an Arduino with a program that has been coded specifically for the condition of stability, although this could equivalently be performed at home with a smaller amperage and iron core. Of course this was not useful in the design of the simplest levitator but if you ask what kind of power sources might be necessary to large scale megastructures such as space elevators that use magnetic field control to lift the rockets most of the way to space large scale power sources and engineering technologies are useful to know about. More generally the Arduino [37] serves as an introduction to more advanced controllers such as PLC controllers [38].

Complex Functions Used In Control Theory and for Voltage Functions in Circuits

Analysis methods such as nodal analysis [39] and mesh analysis [40] are constituent of the underlying laws of circuit theory such as Ohm's Law [41] and Kirchoff's Voltage Law [42]. Most of the laws used in electrical engineering were discovered empirically. The theoretical and mathematical understanding in these cases comes after the discovery, and after many years of refinement from many Mathematicians, Physicists and Scientists, we are able to apply in what some people call a rudimentary application, the theory of electrodynamics to derive these laws. I would not really call his simple but rather standard undergraduate material in Physics. The usefulness of the theoretical apparatus of physics such as Electrodynamics comes from the fact that because the discoveries were made years ago, one does not physically need to see the object to discuss it, perform calculations, and model the circuit before it is actually built. This is exactly the usefulness of mathematical models for circuits. Software such as Pspice [43] exists for solving circuits by solving the underlying mathematical model, practically eliminating the need to know how to actually perform the calculations all but still it is important to understand the theoretical underpinnings of such technologies.

A difficulty that I have noticed is that the theoreticians do not in all respects speak the same approximate language one is forced to adapt when inventing something. A lot of the times when searching through patents and textbooks or articles people might use the exact equation you know well but in an unfamiliar way or with variables and symbols that differ from source to source. I expect AI will eventually make it easier to find the information that we need faster than I have been able to find it using the same methods essentially. Theoreticians need precision, but when something is first designed, mistakes will be made, and often times, as in history, mistakes turn into understanding because they show the flaw in the theoretical ideas, which is obviously the case in the real world that we live in. In theory, digging a hole which is 6 feet deep to place the pole exactly at 40 feet above the ground is a piece of cake, until you begin to dig and find unmarked or unreported gas piping 4 feet deep, then all

of a sudden, the theoretical model of the electrical pole becomes changed, although shifting the pole to the right one foot is approximately the same. The theoretician sees the problem that is induced by adding together a bunch of approximate answers shifted by a foot with respect to the original plan, and understands easily that if this is done over and over during the whole project, all of the small differences in actuality and theory will sum to be a noticeable difference in desired outcome. And speaking to theoreticians, likewise, I can see also how they would get upset with such “practical issues” and that is because if such a change with respect to the model is not compensated for, the construction of the project will be way over the original budget which has been calculated with respect to the original plan. This was my original perspective but in hindsight I think that there are theoretical issues that the practitioner faces which are not well defined and in many instances can not be well defined and these are essentially terms in some cases need to be added to the equations as unknowns relative to the original plan. This is an effective strategy in a real time artificial intelligence acquisition system that adapts as plans change.

As written about by Harvey Brooks in his biography on Hendrik Wade Bode [44] “During World War Two, Bode participated in the development of electrical fire control devices, receiving the Presidential Certificate of Merit in 1948 for his contributions. After the war, he continued his work on military system development, which included artillery fire control and tracking systems for antiaircraft missiles and later for antiballistic missile systems. He specialized in command-and-control communications systems.” A patent of Bode’s in 1938 was on the design of the feedback amplifier. Written within his patent, “Amplifier,” [45], “If the feedback voltage is equal to or greater than the effective input voltage, the amplifier is unstable, but if the feedback voltage is less than the input Voltage, there is no instability. An exceptional case is illustrated in Nyquist Patent 1,915,440, issued June 27, 1933. However, the type of Stability therein disclosed is not absolute and such Systems tend to become unstable when the amplifier gain is reduced.” Within that patent, Bode discusses the mathematical theorems which allowed for him to understand how to design a functioning feedback control circuit. Bode’s book, “Network Analysis and Feedback Amplifier Design,” [46] published in 1945 describes the connection of the differential equation which describes the circuit to the complex-phasor interpretation of the differential equation. In this book, Bode also goes into detail on the Nyquist stability criteria and control circuits.

As the legend seems to go, apparently Harold Black wrote his discovery on a Blank page of the New York Times which led to the negative feedback design. In his biography on H. Black, “Opening Black’s Box Rethinking Feedback’s Myth of Origin,” David A. Mindell writes [47]: “Negative-feedback amplifiers emerged from efforts to extend the telephone network across the continent, to increase the network’s carrying capacity, and to make it work predictably in the face of changes in season, weather, and landscape—from the context, that is, of building a large technical system and operating it over a diverse and extended geography.” Harold Black’s contributions were certainly important for that of today’s developments, and from engineers such as Charles Proteus Steinmetz. In an article, “Harold Black and the Negative Feed-back Amplifier,” [48] Ronald Kline writes, “Black then had an important insight that helped him “reframe” the problem. He recalled that in 1923, “I attended a lecture by C. P. Steinmetz [chief engineer at General Electric] at an AEE meeting [the American Institute of Electrical Engineers, a forerunner of the IEEE] and was impressed by the Steinmetz way of getting down to the fundamentals of a problem.” In his paper, “Stabilized Feedback Amplifiers,” [49] Black discusses the complex definition of the gain for the amplifier: “The effect of adding feed-back, therefore, usually is to change the gain of the amplifier and this change will be expressed as $G_{CF} = 20 \log_{10} \left| \frac{1}{1-\mu\beta} \right|$ where G_{CF} is *db* change in gain due to feed-back.”

In Harry Nyquist’s 1928 paper, he discusses the relationship of the “Certain Topics in Telegraph Transmission Theory” [50] “A simple telegraph system is obtained by connecting a stepped signal element. A telegraph key and battery in series with a line at end, the other end of the line being connected to a sounder, both ends of the system being grounded.” Nyquist is the man responsible for the Nyquist plots that are used here to analyze the symmetry of the Riemann Zeta Function. Obituary statement of Harry Nyquist in 1977 IEEE transactions on automatic control [51], “Nyquist finished his formal education with a Ph.D. degree in physics

from Yale University in 1917. He was immediately employed by the A.T.&T. Company, and spent essentially the rest of his life with the Bell System, either with the A.T.&T. Company's so-called D&R Department, or with Bell Laboratories".

In his Regeneration Theory paper, Nyquist writes [52], "Let the complex quantity $AJ(i\omega)$ represent the ratio by which the amplifier and feed-back circuit modify the current in one round trip, that is, let the magnitude of AJ represent the ratio numerically and let the angle of AJ represent the phase shift. It will be convenient to refer to AJ as an admittance, although it does not have the dimensions of the quantity usually so called. Let the current be impressed on the circuit.

$$I_0 = \cos(\omega t) = \text{Real part of } e^{i\omega t} \quad \text{Eq 1)}$$

The first round trip is then represented by

$$I_1 = \text{Real part of } AJ(j\omega)e^{i\omega t} \quad \text{Eq 2)}$$

And the n th by

$$I_n = \text{Real part of } A^n J^n(j\omega)e^{i\omega t} \quad \text{Eq 3)}$$

The total current of the original impressed current and the first n round trips is

$$I_n = \text{Real part of } e^{i\omega t} \sum_{k=1}^n A^k J^k(j\omega)$$

If the expression in parentheses converges as n increases indefinitely, the conclusion is that the total current equals the limit as n increases indefinitely. Now

$$e^{i\omega t} \sum_{k=1}^n A^k J^k(j\omega) = \frac{(1 - A^{n+1} J^{n+1}(j\omega))}{(1 - AJ)} \quad \text{Eq 4)}$$

If $|AJ| < 1$ this converges to $\frac{1}{1 - AJ}$ which leads to an answer which accords with experiment.

A is here the amplifying ratio, or gain of the amplifier. With these concepts, Nyquist showed how feedback amplification must mathematically work, given of course the simplifications he made in his paper. In his paper, Nyquist uses concepts such as the Fourier Transformation, and Contour integrals in the complex plane to describe this circuit. Apparently some of the results of his paper can be shown using complex analysis theorems such as the Cauchy Argument Principle.

The Laplace transform is named after Pierre-Simon Laplace, and variations of these integral transformations such as the Mellin Transformation had been used by Euler, or at least, transformation similar to it. The Mellin Transformation actually can reduce to the Laplace Transformation, and the Laplace Transformation can reduce to the Fourier Transformation which is what much of AC circuit theory is based upon. The voltages and currents are represented by these sums, as will be shown in the following section for the output of a feedback control system. The Mellin Transformation is additionally related to the concepts of the RZF. This is one of the main connections which compelled me to pursue this endeavor, because then it was obviously not a guess that the concepts of the RZF needed enhanced by the graphical methods of Bode and Nyquist and it also gives a way to relate the fields through the mathematical models. A few simple numerical experiments as shown in the coming sections were seemingly able to provide sufficient evidence of the symmetry conditions for the complex zeros of the RZF.

The Laplace transformation method and other methods are very useful in engineering applications such as the circuit solutions in "Fundamentals of Electric Circuits," by Charles Alexander, a very knowledgeable and helpful instructor who was my previous professor at CSU for Circuits, and second author Matt Sadiku [53].

Additionally, the Laplace and Fourier Transformations allow for the conversion of a differential equation into an algebraic equation which is solvable, and then after solving the easier algebraic equation, the inverse Laplace or Fourier Transformation of the obtained solution yields a solution to the transient differential equation. These integral transformations can be useful therefore, and generalization of it, for solving differential equations. The roots of the differential equation resulting from the transformation of the differential equation into an n th order polynomial equation are of course related to the differential equation solution in the transient domain for the general nonlinear system. Leonhard Euler, who discovered the well known exponential equation, $e^{i\theta} = \cos(\theta) + i\sin(\theta)$, with the manipulation of infinite sums knew of these integral equations and used them in 1774. Laplace Transformation tables exist so that one can save time for achieving the actual goal of using the Laplace Transformation which is not solving integrals: solving a differential equation which describes a circuit or some other realizable physical phenomena, so that the mathematics becomes a real world tool.

The Fourier Series takes the general form:

$$f(t) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \cos(\omega_n t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n \sin(\omega_n t) \quad \text{Eq 5)}$$

The Fourier Series may likewise be defined as the sum of sines and cosines which can be in turn written as a complex number through the Euler equation, as:

$$f(t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n (e^{\alpha} + e^{-\alpha}) + \frac{i}{2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} B_n (e^{-\alpha} - e^{\alpha}) \quad \text{Eq 6)}$$

Where $\alpha \rightarrow \alpha(n, t)$.

The heat diffusion equation is named after Fourier from his pioneering mathematical methods such as in “Analytical Theory of Heat,” [54]. Apparently the Fourier Techniques have already been extended and are used in analyses in Biomedical Engineering such as “A. Spiegl, P. Steinbigler, I. Schmucking, A. Knez and R. Haberl, “Analysis of beat-to-beat variability of frequency contents in the electrocardiogram using two-dimensional Fourier transforms” [55], “SBSV is a new approach to investigate beat-to-beat variabilities of frequency contents in the ECG, combining the SNR of signal averaging with a single-beat analysis,” which was published in 1998. Apparently, in 1843 Hilbert introduced generalized complex numbers called quaternions as discussed in “Relationships Among Various 2-D Quaternion Fourier Transforms” by Min-Hung Yeh [56], which can be used to define a set of generalized 2-D Quaternion Fourier Transformations. Fourier Transformation techniques are also known to be useful for image processing such as the reconstruction of a DNA helix with Coherent Diffraction Imaging techniques. Techniques as such can be used for reconstructing the DNA helix through the implementation of a numerical algorithm.

In this paper he created something today known as the Riemann Zeta Function, which is a generalization of the sum which defines the Euler Product to the complex plane through a method called analytic continuation. The Riemann Zeta Function is very closely related to the complex methods for control theory as used by Nyquist. Riemann was a very prolific writer. He had many publications and contributions to mathematics that many undergraduates know such as “Riemann Sums,” which are taught in first year calculus. He also published papers in various different areas of science and physics such as electrodynamics which are available within archives of his work. The work of Riemann also laid the framework from which the modern theory of Gravity, General Relativity is built, to provide one example.

Complex Algebra in Circuit Theory

The Taylor expansion can be extended to complex numbers if the functions follow certain criteria [57]. Many of the definitions of Complex analysis result as trivial with respect to the single variable calculus, which

can be seen by the setting of the imaginary part of the complex variable to 0 to consider the functions on the real line. The Taylor Theorem was given to me from my first Calculus professor P. Zachlin [58], as a problem: design a mathematical proof of the Taylor Theorem. This gave me great joy during my freshman year. Extending Taylor's Theorem to the complex domain shows how, if one considers that the functions will have derivatives which require chain rule application, how the functions themselves will change with new coordinates which are perhaps nonlinear functions of the original coordinates.. With this, one can see how in some instances nonlinear coordinate transformations are going to yield very challenging complex root equations, and which are likely not analytically possible to solve for in a quick manner. Being able to solve root equations resulting from complex coordinates is something which I have sought to do since understanding that all of physics reduces to differential equations and differential equations can be transformed into root equations. The Partial Differential Equations from Maxwell's Equations reduce to the basic Laws such as ohm's law and how they reduce to the differential equations which describe a circuit.

Another very similar case to solving circuit systems mathematically with transformation methods as was discussed within my Optical Materials course at CSU can be found such as those in multilayered optical media in which the components of the electromagnetic fields may be found by using what is known as a "Transfer Matrix," and then the corresponding transmitted and reflected electromagnetic radiation may be solved for. What is very interesting is that the circuit variables when solving for the currents and voltages will take a similar mathematical form to that of this method. What this method describes is equally described with the powerful techniques known as the Fresnel Equations.

Semi-log Magnitude and Phase Plots of Riemann Zeta Transfer Function

Bode plots are useful in linear circuit theory for modeling phenomena such as the bandpass filter. This section will show the 3-D Bode plots, or 2-D time varying plots of the Riemann Zeta Transfer Function. The Bode Plot can be hand approximated using straight lines in the linear case, however, it is when nonlinear systems are considered that the Bode Plot is no longer the main technique for analyzing circuit stability.

The magnitude and phase plots both will be 3-Dimensional functions. Again, this is because the Riemann Zeta Transfer Function is a function of alpha and beta, so both the phase and the magnitude vary over both parameters. I have also put other versions of these simulations using Desmos on my YouTube so I know the 3d plots can be done as 2d plots that vary in time.

Bode Plots use asymptotic lines to approximate the response. The idea is to use the same approximation and graph responses as Bode for the Real and Imaginary parts of both of these functions. Due to the intrinsic relationship of symmetry to the definition of stability in the frequency domain analysis, we should expect that the critical line is the only place which exhibits the stability criterion seen on a Bode Plot. Plotting the real and imaginary parts of the RZF and RZF' can be done because these sums take a similar form as the Frequency Response output for the filter circuit. Overlaying a plot of these functions we will achieve two separate 3-D Frequency Response type graphs a Phase- $\alpha - \beta$ plot and a Magnitude-- $\alpha - \beta$ using Bode scaling. From these plots, the imaginary system can be analyzed. Note that this is merely a numerical exercise which utilizes the Bode Plots of engineering.

Plotting the RZTF and the RZTF' separately so that we can see their evolution in time separately and how they correspond at the critical value. Plotting them as one function would show the same separate plots but under a single parameterization, so of course the values will take a different definition. In other words, the Bode plots of the RZTF are laid over top of the Bode Plots of the RZTF' so to analyze the functions respectively because the definitions are relative. By doing this, the separate entities can be visualized in time or as surface plots and the intersections are the points where the functions can be zero.

Nyquist Plots:

Gain variations indicate how much uncertainty can be tolerated. Negative one is the point of instability which is desired not to be encircled when taking the Nyquist contour over the polar plot. “The main goal of the stability analysis is to design an initial functioning circuit, which is defined as G_p , the plant, and then using the Feedback mechanism and studying these curves, a G_c , PID controller is added in series with the circuit so that the adjusted piece which is designed given the data, and this portion is what modifies the current to seek the stability condition,” from Z. Gao’s Lecture notes.

The major difference in the methods of the traditional magnitude and phase plots that I have introduced in this paper are the comparing of one function the RZTF to the second function, and in this case, the RZTF’. The idea is that the intersections of these graphs give us information about symmetry and zeros, and the Bode and Nyquist plots will give us information about the stability of the Riemann Zeta Transfer Function. The method of multiple overlaid plots gives a way to relatively analyze the data and to relatively analyze the stability of the RZTF to the RZTF’.

A Nyquist plot of the RZTF is what will allow for the stability criteria to be seen at the critical line. The way that the stability conditions could be analyzed is by comparing the Nyquist plot of the RZTF with the Nyquist plot of the RZTF’. The construction of the Nyquist plot of the RZTF would have to be an contour integral applied to the 3-D polar plot of the RZTF. The condition for the zeros of the RZTF is that the 3-D Nyquist plot of the RZTF overlaps the 3-D Nyquist plot of the RZTF’. Being able to see the Nyquist plot evolve in time will show how the stability of the circuit evolves with respect to the variation which is the parameter. In the case of the RZTF, the evolution of the plots in time of the Nyquist plot will effectively be another way to accomplish the same task which has already been done with the 3-D time simulation and a Bode plot of the RZTF, and is gratuitous to determine that the stability conditions of the RZTF are met anywhere other than the half line because of both the continuity of the simulation over the parameter, and the explicit fact that the Bode Plot stability conditions are met only at the critical line. The reason the visual images later on will show this is true is that the RZTF’ and the RZTF only intersect at $x = 5.$, in addition to the fact that the two relative maximal values, such as for $Xi(s)$, which is a function of the RZF, are at 1 and 0 for both surfaces. It is obvious that by nature of the method used to plot the function that there is only one candidate for the symmetry condition necessary for the RH to be true because of how there is no intersection or maximal values to consider, and this is because of the fact that the coordinate transformation which makes the functional equation true, is true when there are zeros; the RZTF itself does not take anywhere else over the domain, the same values as the RZTF’ by design. This is so the zeros which are defined by the simultaneous intersection of many surfaces, as can be seen with the several different types of parameterization. Inherently this does not prove that only the zeros can lie at the half line, but rather, specifically, the symmetry condition which must be true for the function to be zero is only met at the half line. This symmetry condition, as is shown later, is necessary for the function to be zero.

One reason that I have made many different types of plots for the RZF, RZTF and RZTF’ aside from those which already exist in literature, is because usually, one method of plotting is excellent for showing some properties of the function which are not immediately obvious with other methods. Changing plotting methods sometimes gives different insights. I have plotted these functions here in Matlab, so where the code is also there to correspond to the plots.

Figure 1 [*1]

The following plot is the same plot, but from a different viewpoint:

Figure 2 [*2]

Figure one and two show a Matlab Plot for the Imaginary Part of the RZF subtracted from imaginary part of the RZF evaluated at the s' coordinate transformation with $s' = 1 - x - iy$. The first two images were ran from $[-2,2]$. Changing the domain to get a better image for a larger scaling, $[-10,10]$ in this case:

Figure 3 [*3]

Zooming in on the surface, and changing viewpoints to look at this function in the critical strip, the following image shows the same maximal values at $x = 1$, and $x = 0$:

Figure 4 [*4]

And the code for these plots is:

```

1 - [X, Y] = meshgrid(-10:.2:10);
2 - Z = (imag(zeta(X+i*Y)) - imag(zeta(1-X-i*Y)));
3 - surf(X, Y, Z);

```

Figure 5 [*5]

The following plots use the same function definitions, but this time for the Real parts.

Figure 6 [*6]

The above viewpoint is obviously more meaningful because it has a nice smooth geometry, so it seems, however, due to how this was plotted, from another viewpoint, as shown in Figure Six, we lose the geometry, and continuity:

Figure 7 [*7]

Where the code for this plot is in the following image:

```

1 - [X,Y] = meshgrid(-2:.2:2);
2 - Z = (real(zeta(X+i*Y)))-(real(zeta(1-X-i*Y)));
3 - surf(X,Y,Z);

```

Figure 8 [*8]

One can very quickly see in the images that depending on the coordinate frame the function is analyzed from, in addition to the plotting method, different information can be gathered about the function. Some of the standard plotting techniques work okay, however what is important to realize is that the method which is used to plot the function additionally will provide different images and also values. What gave the most information was not switching from method to method, but using a single method, and changing it to see relatively what the values mean for the different plots. As such is the basis of “Relatively Comparing” data. It is obvious that it depends on the method as to how the data was collected, its viewpoint, and meaning of data, and the RZF shows this specifically because it is a Complex Function which is multivalued.

Mathematical Basis of Nonlinear Controller for Magnetic Levitation

The transfer function $G(s)$ which describes a circuit component is defined as:

$$G(s) = \frac{Y(s)}{u(s)} \quad \text{Eq 7}$$

Which when evaluated along the real line will produce a function of the angular frequency, ω :

$$G(j\omega) = |G(j\omega)| \angle G(j\omega) \quad \text{Eq 8}$$

Figure 9 [*9]

$$Y(j\omega) = G(j\omega)F(j\omega) \quad \text{Eq 9}$$

The Inverse Fourier or Laplace Transformation would yield a transient output response:

$$y(t) = F_0 G_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} F_n G_n \cos(k\omega_0 t + \theta_k + \angle G(j\omega)) \quad \text{Eq 10}$$

A smooth transition of the gain of the amplifier in the circuit by smoothly incrementing or decrementing the variable resistor will cause the Nyquist plot to continuously evolve in time. If the resistor is changed only by a small amount, it should be expected that there is a deviation away from a stabilized levitation.

From the article, “Design and Implementation of a Digital Compensator for a Magnetic Levitation Kit,” Jung-Ho Moon and Myunggon Yoon [59] “open loop transfer function with the controller $C(s)$ set to 1 was expressed as

$$C(s)G(s)H(s) = \frac{(31.94s^2 + 1888)}{s^3 + 173s^2 - 108.4s - 18750} \quad \text{Eq 11}$$

The Frequency Response and Nyquist plots of this plant and controller implementation were discussed within Moon and Yoon’s paper. Which agrees with their figure two which has the caption “The Nyquist plot of the open-loop transfer function with a unity- gain proportional controller:

Figure 10 [*10]

And the code in Matlab for this plot is shown in the following image:

```
1 - H = tf([31.94 0 1888],[1 173 -108.4 18750]);
2 - nyquist(H)
```

Figure 11 [*11]

They have also plotted their compensator function, and the discretized description from the Z transform of the compensator s domain which allows for the compensator values to be tested by looking in the low frequency range of the response which is the Nyquist plot. The Z transform acts on data to represent it as a continuous function in the s domain. This data serves as a basis to compare my experiment's data to, and it also is consistent with other plants and controllers in the literature.

Within the Figure Eight is an arbitrary controller with plant function $G_p(s)$, and compensator function $G_c(s)$. These are effectively “black boxes,” where in my case, the compensator is the Arduino and feedback mechanism, and the plant is consistent of the electromagnet and the components necessary to make it function properly such as the variable resistor. The circular symbol is called the summing point and is representative of the voltage which is the error produced from the position being sensed.

Figure 12 [*12]

The system [60] described by the plant is analyzed with a frequency analysis and then a controller inserts signals $G_c(s)$ to control the system. This is in the linear case, where there are two poles in the denominator are easily controlled with the PID controller implementation where k_p and k'_p are to be determined. There are other methods for tuning the system to attain stability, and additionally, when the nonlinear domain is stepped into, this

method can not be applied. The feedback system which is the magnetic levitation system is unstable, so effort has to go into finding the stability locations of the magnetic levitation device, and apparently be best method for finding the stability conditions for the magnetic levitation device is that of the Nyquist stability method, or root locus method.

Compensator Factors with controllable parameters, k_s, k'_i, α, β can be written as:

$$\left(k_s + \frac{k'_i}{s}\right) \left(\frac{\alpha s + 1}{\beta s + 1}\right) \quad \text{Eq 12)}$$

For a series inductive-resistive circuit, the describing differential equation is:

$$V_s = i_L R + L \frac{di_L}{dt} \quad \text{Eq 13)}$$

Where a Laplace Transformation with $s = \alpha + i\beta$, the equation becomes:

$$V_s(s) = I(s)R + sLI(s) \quad \text{Eq 14)}$$

Where the resulting Transfer Function of this circuit is:

$$\frac{1}{R + sL} = \frac{I_L(s)}{V_s(s)} \quad \text{Eq 15)}$$

Partial Fraction Expansion after putting in a step voltage $u(t)$ is:

$$\frac{1}{s(R + Ls)} = \frac{k_1}{\left(s + \frac{R}{L}\right)} + \frac{k_2}{s} \rightarrow k_1 e^{-\frac{Rt}{L}} + k_2 u_s(t) \quad \text{Eq 16)}$$

The step function can be used to observe the response of the circuit because the step function is $\frac{1}{s}$. Control in this circuit comes from controlling the current input. The Frequency Response based design is called “loop shaping,” where the plant transfer function provides a Nyquist plot for a possibly, and the Nyquist plot is shaped until it becomes a curve where the stability conditions are met.

In Nyquist’s 1930 paper “Regeneration Theory,” [52] the function in equation h) describe the circuit quantity known as the voltage, which aside from the impedance and current which can be described in complex or phasor notation in AC circuits provides the useful information for the circuit that can be used to control the magnetic fields depending on the position of the magnetic object as seen with a position sensor.

An experiment performed within “An active disturbance rejection control of leader-follower Thomson’s jumping ring,” Herbert Ramirez et al. [61] shows how an error control implementation allows for the tracking of the conductive rings to levitate due to the fact that they have an induced current which produces a magnetic dipole moment in opposition of the flux which is changing through the area of the circuit from the voltage controlled current from a pair of electromagnetic coils. The current is controlled by Active Disturbance Rejection Techniques. Equations 21) and 22) of Ramirez’s paper are the coupled differential equations which describe the force on the rings, where in physics, these equations are called the Equations of Motion, and may be derived by the Euler Lagrange equations. The physical apparatus and circuit connections can be seen in Figure Three, which is Figure three in their experiment: PID controllers, as from Z. Gao’s “Active Disturbance Rejection Control,” [62] have the following solution:

$$u = k_p + k_1 \int edt + k_d \dot{e}. \quad \text{Eq 17)}$$

The above equation represents a series RLC load which has control parameters k_p, k_i, k_d . Controlling these circuit parameters controls the current draw, and therefore controls the voltage in the load that does the

lifting of the ball. In the flat, linear system modeled by the Thompson Ring Experiment, the control parameters are manually controlled. One should expect that in the nonlinear case, this would be extraordinarily difficult, and that the control parameters might vary in time as would be done for complicated compound processes built from these methods. This is effectively achieved by controlling the gain of the operational amplifier.

If multiple electromagnets were added in series, there would be inductive terms in the plant transfer function. This type of circuit, if designed properly could be that of controlling the trajectory of magnetic balls within tubes, much like which occurs for the intrinsic magnetic dipoles of the charged particles which are accelerated within the acceleration chambers at CERN [63].

Mathematical Methodology in Circuit Theory

	ME's In Differential Form	ME's In Integral Form	Name
1	$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0}$	$\oiint \vec{E} \cdot d\vec{a} = \frac{Q_{enclosed}}{\epsilon_0}$	Gauss' Law (Electric)
2	$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t}$	$\oint \vec{E} \cdot d\vec{l} = -\frac{d}{dt} (Mag. Flux)$	Faraday-Lenz
3	$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0$	$\oiint \vec{B} \cdot d\vec{a} = 0$	Gauss' Law (Magnetic)
4	$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \mu_0 \vec{J} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t}$	$\oint \vec{B} \cdot d\vec{l} = \mu_0 I_{enclosed} + \frac{1}{c^2} \left(\frac{d}{dt} (Elect. Flux) \right)$	Ampere-Maxwell

Units	Circuit Component	Characteristic Equation	Relation to Electrostatics
Ohms	Resistor	$R = \frac{V}{I}$	Ohm's Law (Electrostatics)
Farads	Capacitor	$\frac{I}{\frac{dV}{dt}} = C$	Polarity of dielectric between capacitive plates
Henries	Inductor	$\frac{V}{\frac{dI}{dt}} = L$	Current/Magnetic Flux relation (ME 4)

The Riemann Hypothesis [64]. A goal of this paper is to show the relation of the mathematical methodology within field theories and particularly Circuit theory to the complex number descriptions used for the Riemann Zeta Function. An example discussed is the relation of the integral that describes the RZF and the Laplace Integral Transformation definition. By looking at the Maxwell Field Equations in the Electromagnetic Wave limit, the solutions may be described by a sum of sinusoids with different amplitudes. General signal distributions and the mathematical methodology of circuit theory exploit the techniques of complex analysis, whereas theories such as General Relativity which are inconsistent with Quantum Field Theories that rely on similar logic avoid it within definitions and derivations.

This is part one of the two sections discussing this material and the connection to circuit theory. This Section is a summary of the research I performed on the connection to mathematical methodology in S.T.E.M, which led me to design "Algorithmic Production," a method for building algorithms and theorems, which ensures that if the theorem or Hypothesis is sufficiently constructed by the underlying rules and theorems, then the theorem or hypothesis is true. Algorithmic production is similar in nature to the functionality of the apparatus of General Relativity, but a purely mathematical method which can be applied to field theories such as General Relativity. I have already made progress in using Algorithmic Production as one of the major pillars needed for Artificial General Intelligence and integrating this technology into the QAS Software platform which automates software tasks and is expanding into other areas of automation such as robotics since these software can be used for the technology development. This along with Large language models and other advances certainly will bring better AGI models.

$$\vec{\nabla}^2 \vec{E} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} = 0 = -\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{B}}{\partial t^2} + \vec{\nabla}^2 \vec{B},$$

MATEHMATICS AND PHYSICS WITHIN CIRCUIT THEORY

Firstly, all of circuit theory hinges on the laws of electrodynamics and all electromagnetic phenomena can be described by Maxwell's Equations (and the Lorentz Force Law) which can be stated as:

These Laws of electromagnetism are the laws solely responsible for the electromagnetic interaction, and can be expressed in many forms. After adding the second term in ME 4), and uncoupling the equations (in modern terms, by comparing the curl of 2) and 3)), he found what we express in modern notation as the wave equation in a region of space containing an electric and magnetic field in the absence of current and charge distributions:

The first of these five equations can be found in virtually and electrodynamics text, such as “Introduction to Electrodynamics” by David Griffiths [64]. Where there is a clear symmetry that the electric and magnetic field possess. The fields are known to be a relativistic effect of the other; e.g, a magnetic field is a relativistic effect of an electrically charged object in motion. The fact that all observers perceive in terms of electromagnetic radiation effectively implies that all observers are relative, but that the laws of physics for one observer should yield the same happening, even if their spatial and temporal perceptions are different. This is what Einstein effectively discovered in 1905 in his paper, “On The Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies,” the fact that the electric field is a relativistic effect of the magnetic field and vice versa implies that if one perceives an event, which has to be done with electromagnetic radiation, the radiation travels through free space (or some other medium) and is intercepted by an electromagnetic instrument designed to observe an event. Because of this, in the case of constant velocity, the Lorentz Transformations which were known at the time of Einstein were used to derive his famous equations of Mass-Energy equivalence such as those stated in “Classical Mechanics,” John R. Taylor, Equation 15.74) and Equation 15.85) [65]:

$$E = mc^2\gamma; \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad \text{Eq 18)}$$

$$E^2 = (mc^2)^2 + (pc)^2 \quad \text{Eq 19)}$$

The electromagnetic radiation which is produced by the sinusoidal acceleration of the electrons within an antenna obeys this wave equation, as well will -in a vacuum- all other electromagnetic radiation which has been created by accelerating charges.

The entirety of circuit theory can be derived with these equations. Because often times it is not a need to find the physical reason that the system ticks the way it does, engineers have built and designed mathematical tools which help one to quickly solve circuit problems. All of these methods require at least an understanding of basic complex analysis. Frequency response methods which are very powerful tools for circuit analysis also utilize complex algebra and calculus.

In generality, the methodology to reduce a linear circuit is to firstly describe the node voltages using some analysis method which in modern times is nodal analysis and mesh analysis, although nodal analysis can always be applied and in the same consistent form. A set of mathematical operations and conceptual rules are applied to a circuit and the circuit variables become related and therefore the circuit is solved, and can be physically built.

A general linear circuit with an AC simulation of a circuit with Inductors, Capacitors, and Resistors has sinusoidal outputs for the voltage and current quantities of the circuit if an AC source is input in the circuit. This is because the circuit quantities for an RLC circuit will produce generally a linear second order differential equation for the circuit variable due to the fact that the characteristic equations of the device components are:

The equations within the above table can be found within “Fundamentals of Electric Circuits,” Charles Alexander. Which makes the n node voltages and currents always describable by the general second order differential equation:

$$A_n \frac{d^2 V_n}{dt^2} + B_n \frac{dV_n}{dt} + C_n V_n + D_n = 0 \quad \text{Eq 20)}$$

$$E_n \frac{d^2 I_n}{dt^2} + F_n \frac{dI_n}{dt} + G_n I_n + H_n = 0 \quad \text{Eq 21)}$$

This linear ordinary second order differential equation can be solved by applying the Laplace or Fourier Transformation technique. When one applies these mathematical transformations to the mathematically described circuit, the meaning of the circuit itself changes, for example when one applies the Laplace transformation technique and translates the variables, what is left is an algebraic equation described in terms of another variable, often s , which is defined over the new domain, the s domain in this case, and effectively the characteristic equations that described the connected devices are able to be replaced by the equivalent algebraic components. In this transformation, s is of course with respect to t , and so therefore solving for the solution in the s domain which is easier to solve because it is algebraic, yields a solution to the differential equations above in algebraic terms and then through a reverse transformation achieve the time domain equivalent description of the circuits. These equations are very similar to the wave equation, but they have additional constants and damping terms.

In an inductive load, the current lags the voltage by 90 degrees. In a three phase Δ connected Δ load, the generator will absorb both Reactive Power and Active Power. When an inductive load is added to a circuit, we expect to find that the Reactive Power, or the Imaginary Power has changed. The phase angle of the impedance can be corrected by adding capacitive components and the power changes in such a process; it is called power factor correction, which is important for minimizing losses in electrical systems. Additionally, by adding capacitive terms, the phase angle changes, and when put in combination with rectifier circuits, capacitors filter the waveform. There is an advantage of describing elements such as capacitors and inductors which have derivative and integral operations for the circuit quantities in the complex domain is and that is because the equations are easy to manipulate, understand, and save time to use contrary to the solution method for solving the differential equations generally which is time consuming and prone to mistakes.

Imagining the Reactive power from an inductive load using the Phasor interpretation in a circuit analysis. Looking numerically at the derivation for the cosine and sine terms for the oscillation, it is known from the solution of the wave equation that the solution can be arrived to from the truncation of the real part of the complex electromagnetic wave solutions that solved Maxwell's equations. The phasor interpretation of power has specific symmetry exhibited with respect to the conjugate definitions. Take for example the complex power and its conjugate:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{s} &= \vec{v}\vec{I}^* = V_{RMS}I_{RMS}e^{j\theta} \\ \vec{s}' &= \vec{v}\vec{I} = V_{RMS}I_{RMS}e^{-j\theta} \end{aligned}$$

The conjugate has mirror symmetry with respect to theta but physically, the flipping is in the vertical. This peculiarity shows that the physical difference between complex systems and Cartesian systems is related by scalings, inversions, and rotations, and other symmetric operations.

RELATION OF THE DESCRIBING DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS TO THE RESULTING SERIES AND GENERAL FOURIER SERIES

The RZF can be written generally as (by inserting $e^{-(x+iy)\ln(n)}$ into $\sum n^{-(x+iy)}$):

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \cos(y \ln(n)) + i \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \sin(y \ln(n)). \quad \text{Eq 22)}$$

With the complex variable being equal to $s = x + iy$. The Fourier Series can be written from Alexander as:

$$f(y) = a_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n \cos(ky) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} B_n \sin(ky) \quad \text{Eq 23)}$$

Where f is a periodic function of y . An $F(y)$ can be formed such that F obeys Poisson's equation, in such a way that F is representative of the electric potential of a system [66]. When the Charge density, which is a function of four variables is zero, F obeys Laplace's equation assuming separation of variables, and the completeness of the constituent functions has a general solutions of the form:

$$V(x, y) = (Ae^x + Be^{-x})(C\sin(ky) + D\cos(ky)) \quad \text{Eq 24)}$$

a more general form would be an infinite sum of the linear combinations:

$$V(x, y) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n e^x + b_n e^{-x}) D_n \sin(ky) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n e^x + b_n e^{-x}) C_n \cos(ky). \quad \text{Eq 25)}$$

Laplace's 2-D partial differential equation is similar in form to the Wave Equation [67] which provides general solutions of the form:

$$\psi(x, t) = C_1 f(ky - \omega t) + C_2 f(ky + \omega t) \quad \text{Eq 26)}$$

The underlying and governing differential equation, or rule which allows for the construction of the function which satisfies this rule, is fundamentally the same differential equation studied with different parameters, aside from complex constants. Remarkably similar even the solution family appears, but they have radically different numerical values and form. With, however, numerical transformations of the variables, the original definitions could be transformed to mean something new, respectively. Allow, for example, the x of the RZF to be zero, and we have something very similar to the function written with a Fourier series, other than the primary difference that the B_n are not complex. This single difference in equation form, causes for an entirely different form of solution because the roots of the analytic function must satisfy the roots of two functions, namely:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sin(y \ln(n)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \cos(y \ln(n)) \quad \text{Eq 27)}$$

(the real and imaginary parts of the RZF)

Whereas the function, $f(y)$ is clearly a single variable function which has only one output. A generalization, however, of this series such as:

$$f(x, y) = a_0(x, y) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n(x, y) \cos(k_n(x, y)y) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} B_n(x, y) \sin(k_n(x, y)y) \quad \text{Eq 28)}$$

leads to amplitudes of the sine and cosine waves which are functions of the coordinates, and also infinitely many families of infinitely many frequencies that the summed waveforms propagate with. This function, which is a generalization of the function which satisfies the Fourier transformation methodology for differential equation solutions, because it is a function of multiple variables as opposed to one and has roots described by two values and not one (a real value and an imaginary value), although with respect to the y variable, is only one function of one variable. Thus, $f(x, y)$ can satisfy a new differential equation which depends on x and y , and still yet, provided a further simplification of the frequencies be a solution to the original differential equation.

Laplace's equation which acts on the function $V(x, y)$ is thus a coordinate transformation of the wave equation which acts on the function $\psi(x, t)$, with the coordinate transformation $y = it$, and a parameterization of the wave velocity. So, certain properties of the functions which obey the Laplace equation also change when we change the form of the differential equation because we have redefined the variables, and in some way related to the solution of the Wave Equation and the functions which are solutions to them. These functions are called Harmonic functions. Very similarly, the Cauchy-Riemann Equations -which are effectively the differential equations by which analytic functions such as the RZF must obey- can be compared under a similar coordinate

transformation and respective redefinition of the variables, as just discussed with the $V(x, y)$ and $\psi(x, t)$. When compared to the Wave Equation, I find that the Cauchy-Riemann conditions are different from the wave equation depending on whether the wave velocity is Imaginary or Real. The hyperbolic equations which the Lorentz equations of SR can be arrived to; produce a singularity when the velocity of the problem is equal to c , and effectively we obtain an infinite value for the energy which breaks the rules of physics and therefore is ruled out of possibility; is the mathematical reason that the speed of light is a universal speed limit. Letting the velocity of the observer be imaginary in this instance avoids this catastrophe for that numerical value: imagine with respect to an observer who uses complex coordinates which is traveling at light speed and instead provides a complex solution, however, very clearly, such an insertion changes the definitions of the original variables. One is effectively outside of the range of electromagnetic propagation. Much should be expected when someone redefines the variables in a relative way which is contrary to experience. This is because the hypotenuse of the measured triangle which obeys $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$ when either leg is an imaginary distance, changes meaning. Consider $b = ik$, then we have a new triangle equation with hypotenuse a . Very clearly in such an instance, imaginary variables have to be defined with respect to the real variables, and one has "analytically continued" or transformed the problem defined over real numbers to the complex domain.

Additional Simulation For Equation 1.2 $f^x = (-f)^x e^{-i\pi x}$, Matlab:

The following 3-D plot is a plot of an exponential function with similar character to the Riemann Zeta Function,

Figure 13 [*13]

plotting the real and imaginary parts:

And the same function viewed from a different viewpoint:

Figure 14 [*14]

Figure 15[*15]

And from the side, with the camera pointing in the direction parallel to the direction of y:

And the code for the above plots is displayed in Figure Nine:

```
1 - [X, Y] = meshgrid(0:.2:10);
2 - Z1 = ((X)^(X)).*(cos(X.*3.14));
3 - Z2 = ((X)^(X)).*(sin(X).*3.14);
4 - Z3 = Z1-Z2;
5 - figure
6 - surf(X, Y, Z1)
7 - hold on
8 - surf(X, Y, Z2)
9 - surf(X, Y, Z3)
10 - hold off
11 - grid on
```

Figure 16 [*16]

Additionally, changing the cosine components from the parameterization to instead be viewed as its own axis, the following graphs are obtained:

Figure 17 [*17]

And the same plot from a different viewpoint can be seen:

Figure 18 [*18]

And the last view, where the surface was zoomed out on, and in a domain where the function takes on huge values, the following plot is obtained:

Figure 19 [*19]

And the Matlab code for figures 12 through 19 can be seen in the following image:

```

1 - [X,Y] = meshgrid(0:.2:10);
2 - Z1 = ((X).^X).*(cos(Y.*3.14));
3 - Z2 = ((X).^X).*(sin(Y.*3.14));
4 - Z3 = Z1-Z2;
5 - figure
6 - surf(X, Y, Z1)
7 - hold on
8 - surf(X, Y, Z2)
9 - surf(X, Y, Z3)
10 - hold off
11 - grid on

```

Figure 20 [*20]

Additionally, a surface plot with contours shows a plot of the Real part of the RZF subtracted from the imaginary part of the RZF. Notice again how this viewpoint and definitions give holes in what should be a continuous surface:

Figure 21 [*21]

Where the code for this plot is able to be seen in figure fifteen:

```

1 - [X,Y] = meshgrid(-2:.2:2);
2 - Z1 = real(zeta(X+i*Y));
3 - Z2 = imag(zeta(X+i*Y));
4 - Z3 = Z1-Z2;
5 - figure
6 - surf(X, Y, Z1)
7 - hold on
8 - surf(X, Y, Z2)
9 - surf(X, Y, Z3)
10 - hold off
11 - grid on

```

Figure 22 [*22]

This usually occurs with an ill-defined domain where complex numbers, infinities or definition break downs appear in places they should not, and in these cases, it is best to compare the data to another plot which gives consistent numbers. As is done in field theories in a different way, this can be used to find domains which are not defined for the function. The errors in a way can be a guide to indicate that the definitions are incorrect. Knowing that this is true, but that the values give that of the RZF, a method which is able to interpret these values in a continuous fashion can be constructed. Most important about analyses is continuity, so when there are definition swapping, and breaks in continuity, those are the places where which are issue. The method discussed here is nothing more than Relatively comparing functions when this domain issue is known to occur.

Simulation of Parameterized Riemann Zeta Transfer Function and Primed Riemann Zeta Transfer Function to Prove Symmetry Conditions for the Complex Zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function

The RZF is a multivalued function. The definition of the zeros of the RZF are that of when the 2-D surface which describes the Real part of the function intersects zero simultaneously as the Imaginary Part of the Function. The Functional Equation evaluated at the critical line indicates that the zeros should possess symmetry if they exist only at the half line, therefore, all complex zeros, if they exist, must be symmetric with respect to the iy axis. To show that this symmetry exists only at the half line, consider two functions, a function created from the real and imaginary parts of the RZF and a second function created from the real and imaginary parts of the RZF evaluated at the coordinate transformation which makes the functional equation true, specifically: $s' = 1 - x - iy$. Running a simulation on a 2-D plane with a parameterization of the coordinates with $y = x$, it can be easily seen that the functions seem to overlap only at the critical line. This is truly a 3-D simulation as it is being operated in time, as it can likewise be seen with a surface plot. $RZF' \equiv \zeta'(x, y) = RZF(s') = \zeta(s') \rightarrow \zeta(x', y') \in \mathbb{C}$.

The Riemann Zeta Transfer Function:

The magnitude of the phasor is:

$$|\zeta(s)| = \sqrt{U_{\zeta}^2 + V_{\zeta}^2} \quad \text{Eq 29}$$

And the complex angle is given by:

$$\phi_{\zeta}(x, y) = \text{Arctan}\left(\frac{U_{\zeta}}{V_{\zeta}}\right) \quad \text{Eq 30}$$

Due simply to the fact that this function is likewise defined as a complex number, Z may likewise be written:

$$Z(x, y) = \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \cos(y \ln(n)) \right) + i \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \sin(y \ln(n)) \right) \quad \text{Eq 31}$$

In this form, a completion of the excel experiment which indicates which approximation is the best, this approximation will be used to output the functions for the 2-D RZTF, and its straight line approximation with Bode Plots. The stability criteria of the regularly scaled Magnitude Plot (because the logarithmic scale usually used is not necessary for observing the properties) at the critical line. The stability criteria of the circuit theory analogy is closely related to the symmetry conditions that I will describe to form the proof. $Z(x, y)$ is transformed to $\zeta(s)$ by analytic continuation so the operation of analytic continuation can be plotted by plotting the transform that converts Z to $\zeta(s)$.

The Primed Riemann Zeta Transfer Function

As would be demanded from a physical theory, a symmetric function with respect to the RZTF should exist if it is to be modeled with the software that I used which is available free to any person who has internet so that the data of the RZTF and RZTF' can everywhere be relatively interpreted over the real domain defined by the 1-D creature. The construction of the RZTF' is designed so that numerically, the function can not overlap with the original function unless the locations are zeros, where then there is intersection, the RZF is zero. Note that the RZF never is equal to the RZTF' unless the function is zero which seems to occur only at the critical line. The particular construction of RZTF' is designed by asserting a negative sign in the definition of the RZTF. Analyzing the RZTF with respect to a RZTF' provides the ability to construct a way to compare the definitions of the functions simultaneously. In this analysis the fact that when the RZF is zero, these two graphs intersect. The construction of the primed RZTF is highly dependent upon the phase angle of RZTF' with respect to RZTF. There is a parameterized Phase and magnitude plot which shows specifically that the function rises with a slope opposite to that of the other function. This symmetry is seen easily without the logarithmic scaling of the Bode Plots. The

theorems of course still retain the same definitions. The parameterized magnitude plot show that the functions overlap at specifically the critical value.

Based upon the results of the Desmos Experiment as described in the next section is that certain RZTF's are easily ruled out of selection upon the basis that the domain of the graph is real. From symmetry, and comparing the functions respectively and thinking of the transformations as coordinate transformations, I construct the RZTF' with the RZF', analogous to the definition of the RZTF and the RZF because then the definitions within the simulation are defined symmetrically.

Definition of RZTF':

$$|Z'(x, y)| = \sqrt{\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \cos(y \ln(n))\right)^2 + \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \sin(y \ln(n))\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq 32}$$

And the complex angle is given by:

$$\phi_{Z'}(x, y) = \angle |Z'(x, y)| = \text{Arctan}\left(\frac{\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \sin(y \ln(n))\right)}{\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \cos(y \ln(n))\right)}\right) \quad \text{Eq 33}$$

Due simply to the fact that this function is likewise defined as a complex number, Z' may likewise be written:

$$Z'(x, y) = \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \cos(y \ln(n))\right) + i \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \sin(y \ln(n))\right) \quad \text{Eq 34}$$

And of course:

$$|\zeta'(s)| = \sqrt{U_{\zeta'}^2 + V_{\zeta'}^2} \quad \text{Eq 35}$$

And the complex angle is given by:

$$\phi_{\zeta}(x', y') = \text{Arctan}\left(\frac{U_{\zeta'}}{V_{\zeta'}}\right) \quad \text{Eq 36}$$

The advantage of analyzing one Transfer Function at the same time as another Transfer function which has the same information as the first is that symmetry can be exploited in the plotting software to obtain information about the functions based on the relative comparing of the two functions.

Only at the critical line should the Riemann Zeta Transfer Function Equation become true, where we should expect symmetry because zeros occur there. By developing a RZTF' that is built in an analogous manner to that of the RZTF and comparing it to the RZTF, the zeros may be relatively compared.

The following video shows the short simulation, "Parameterized Simulation of Unprimed Riemann Zeta Transfer Function relatively to the primed RZTF," [68] shows a time simulation of the two functions. Due to the fact that there must be continuity in time if this is an analytic function which has been parameterized, the symmetry can be seen from observing how the phase angle diagram changes in time which is scaled in normal units. The construction of the RZTF and the RZTF in the manner shown in the video provides an image of a 3-D function which can easily be plotted with colored surfaces also, but then the definitions of the zeros are locatable by the intersection of the surfaces. Locating these intersections usually is best done numerically, as an exact algorithm would take even by hand to compute an infinite time to write and is therefore impossible. A numerical simulation may not be able to prove that all intersecting surfaces occur at the critical line, however, a numerical simulation with the proper method for interpreting the data can prove that properties such as symmetry exist. The way I think most accessible in modern times is that of what Electrical Engineers have been doing over the last decade, and that is Bode and Nyquist plots. The plot in this video is a semi-log plot. It is just the natural logarithm of the magnitude of the RZTF. The Bode Plot parameterization video is sufficient for showing that the symmetry

properties exist by watching the graph change in time. Zeros require both symmetry and intersections of the red and green lines in the phase, and the magnitude requires an overlapping of the lines. One can see, that over the relevant domain of the function, even though, the long term activity is the same, these properties are clearly only met, as there is a linear progression in time. One graph accelerates towards the other graph. There are no discontinuities, and oscillations. This simulation considers only the first 50 terms because the approximation is enough to show that the desired symmetry property exists.

A plot of the magnitude of the RZTF and RZTF' can be seen in the figure one:

Figure 23 [*23]

Where the code for this plot can be seen in the following image:

```

1 - [X,Y] = meshgrid(-2:.2:2);
2 - Z1 = (real(zeta(X+i*Y))^2+((imag(zeta(X+i*Y)))^2))^1/2;
3 - Z2 = (((real(zeta(1-X-i*Y))))^2+((imag(zeta(1-X-i*Y)))^2))^1/2;
4 - surf(X,Y,Z1);
5 - surf(X,Y,Z2);

```

Figure 24 [*24]

The following image shows a 3-D visualization of the parameterized RZTF and RZTF' time simulation, however in this image, the interpretation is easier to understand. Specifically, the intersection of the two functions is at $x = .5$, and the maximal values of either surface is half a unit away. Notice how over the relevant domain, the surfaces are curved in opposite manners, and this is because one function is a function of the backwards moving coordinate, namely negative x and y .

Figure 25 [*25]

Where the Matlab code for this plot is displayed in figure four:

```

1 - [X,Y] = meshgrid(-2:.01:2);
2 - Z1 = (real(zeta(X+i*Y))).^2;
3 - Z2 = (imag(zeta(X+i*Y))).^2;
4 - Z3 = log(sqrt(Z1+Z2));
5 - Z1 = (real(zeta(1-X-i*Y))).^2;
6 - Z2 = (imag(zeta(1-X-i*Y))).^2;
7 - Z3 = log(sqrt(Z1+Z2));
8 - figure
9 - surf(X, Y, Z1)
10 - hold on
11 - surf(X, Y, Z2)
12 - hold off
13 - grid on

```

Figure 26 [*26]

The following image is a plot of the Logarithm of the magnitude of the RZTF:

Figure 27 [*27]

And the following image shows a plot of the logarithm of the magnitude of the primed Riemann zeta transfer function:

Figure 28 [*28]

With this plotting method and these scaling, the phase plot for the RZTF and RZTF' are both not as revealing when it comes to this property. Using logarithmic scaling, the following image shows the phase plot of the RZTF:

Figure 29 [*29]

Where only Z6 was selected to be plotted with contours in this image, the following code was as in figure eight:

```

Untitled3test.m  X  +
1 - [X,Y] = meshgrid(-2:.09:2);
2 - Z1 = (real(zeta(X+i*Y)));
3 - Z2 = (imag(zeta(X+i*Y)));
4 - Z3 = atan((Z2)/(Z1));
5 - Z4 = (real(zeta(1-X-i*Y)));
6 - Z5 = (imag(zeta(1-X-i*Y)));
7 - Z6 = atan((Z4)/(Z5));
8 - figure
9 - surf(X, Y, Z3)
10 - hold on
11 - surf(X, Y, Z6)
12 - hold off
13 - grid on

```

Figure 30 [*30]

The RZTF and RZTF' phase plots are not as revealing as the time simulation or magnitude plots, and it is best to use an alternate plotting method to see the specific symmetry desired, however, the Phase and magnitude plots together make the whole picture. Combine that to the time simulation or 4-D simulations with an extra parameter, and one can then begin to visualize why the RZF has these specific properties.

Overlaying the phase plot of the RZTF and RZTF', the following plot is obtained:

Figure 31 [*31]

And with Logarithmic Scaling the phase plot does not become any more clear, however, the phase plot for the time simulation in the Desmos video showed that the symmetry properties is met for the phase angle only at the critical line also.

Theory and Physics for the Voltage Controlled Levitation Device

The Thompson Jumping Ring Experiment has an electromagnetic coil which has a conducting ring placed on the top of the coil, and often times an iron core for increasing the intensity of the magnetic field of the coil as is used within my experiment. Before one considers moving the ring with a coil, it might be natural to inquire such as this research group has, as written within the article, “Single-Ring Magnetic Levitation Configuration for Object Manipulation and Density-Based Measurement,” Chengqian Zhang, et al [69], “This configuration can levitate diamagnetic materials in paramagnetic solutions under an applied magnetic field below 0.5 T, which is created by two rectangular permanent magnets (50 mm × 50 mm × 25 mm) at a distance of 45 mm with like poles facing each other, as shown in Figure S1 in the Supporting Information.” The group also investigated the strength of the magnetic field from permanent magnets required for magnetic ring levitation. In such a case, both of the objects which are interacting each possess a magnetic dipole moment. Note that a direct consequence of the magnetic Gauss’ Law, there are no such thing as magnetic monopoles. In this case, the magnetic field which exists due to the fact that current is flowing through the coil, acts on the magnetic dipole moment which exists for the second ring, ultimately causing a force on the second which allows for stable levitation to occur supposing the correct magnetic field strengths. This experiment requires an AC power supply. The Thompson Jumping Ring experiment, which still has a levitating ring, operates, although with the same equations, in a different manner. The Thompson Ring Experiment is set up by connecting an AC power supply to a coil which has an extended iron core for amplification of the magnetic field produced from the current going through the wire of the core.

For a neodymium ball, a Matlab simulation can be used to show how the magnetic field will permeate the surrounding space, as shown in figure 31:

Figure 32 [*32]

Figure 33 [*33]

The magnetic field which is created from the coil apparatus pierces the area of the conducting ring, and due to the Faraday-Lenz Law, an ElectroMotive Force is generated within the conductor, which could be represented as a simple resistive circuit. As the electrons begin to move within the conductor because of the magnetic field of the coil, an induced magnetic dipole moment will exist in opposition of the coil's magnetic field. What results is that the ring jumps away from the coil against gravity. This action on the outside seems similar to that of moving a ferromagnetic material as such in my experiment, however, the underlying physics is different because the construction of the magnetic material occurs from different reasons.

As can be seen with conductors, the "magnetic history" of some objects indeed matters, as magnetic materials such as diamagnetic materials do not have magnetic fields unless the material resides within a magnetic field. There are three main types of magnetic materials, and they are called Paramagnetic, Diamagnetic, and Ferromagnetic.

From "Fundamentals of Physics," Jearl Walker and Halliday Resnick, chapter 32, page 958 [70], "A diamagnetic material placed in an external magnetic field \vec{B}_{ext} develops a magnetic dipole moment directed opposite \vec{B}_{ext} . If the field is non-uniform, the diamagnetic material is repelled *from* a region of greater magnetic field *toward* a region of lesser field." Apparently frogs can be levitated by the action of a magnetic field from a solenoid. As Jearl discusses briefly, even frogs which are diamagnetic can be levitated through the application of a sufficiently strong external magnetic field because the intrinsic dipole moments align to produce a net extrinsic dipole moment.

Another type of magnetic material is called paramagnetic material. Also from "Fundamentals of Physics," Jearl Walker and Halliday Resnick, Chapter 32, page 959 [71], "A paramagnetic material placed in an external magnetic field \vec{B}_{ext} develops a magnetic dipole moment in the direction of \vec{B}_{ext} . If the field is non-uniform, the paramagnetic material is attracted toward a region of greater magnetic field from a region of lesser magnetic field. In other words, as opposed to the permanent dipole moment which exists such as in ferromagnetic materials, the intrinsic properties which define the materials are fundamentally different and this results in a different relative arrangement of the atoms which causes for the material to behave in different fashions.

Experiments such as written about within "Tilted Magnetic Levitation Enables Measurement of the Complete Range of Densities of Materials with Low Magnetic Permeability," by Alex Nemiroski, et al [72] show how when diamagnetic materials are suspended within a paramagnetic medium within an external magnetic field, the density of objects can be calculated based upon the measured displacement from the center of the paramagnetic medium: "A nonmagnetic sample, with density ρ_s , levitates in the paramagnetic solution due to the balance of two forces: the gravitational (i.e., buoyant) force F_g caused by a difference in density between the solution and the sample and the magnetic force F_m . The magnetic force originates from the difference in the magnetic energy density between the paramagnetic solution and the diamagnetic (or weakly paramagnetic) object: it is more energetically favorable for a volume of paramagnetic solution to be in a region of high magnetic field (i.e., close to the faces of the magnets) than for the same volume of a nonmagnetic object." Apparently the paramagnetic medium which supplied the magnetic field consisted of a fluid with paramagnetic salt dissolved within it. The research group showed that the magnetic field gradient was strong enough to displace the nonmagnetic materials within the medium. The tilting of the apparatus allowed for the team to determine how strong the magnetic force on the object is from gravity when it was positioned in its stable state.

From "Fundamentals of Physics," Jearl Walker, chapter 32, page 963, "A ferromagnetic material placed in an external magnetic field \vec{B}_{ext} develops a strong magnetic dipole moment in the direction of \vec{B}_{ext} . If the field is nonuniform, the ferromagnetic material is attracted toward a region of greater magnetic field from a region of lesser field."

Particle accelerators work on the principles very similar to that here. If many of these coils were placed in series, there would be inductive terms, and the ball could perhaps be guided by different shaped tubes. The coils would be placed so that the ball is pushed out from one coils at the same time that the second coil is pulling the ball. The net action would be an acceleration, and if there are many coils each paired in time to do this properly, the result would be a ball accelerator which could probably be controlled with similar techniques, although a problem which seems would be faced is the number of sensors required for putting a ball within a circular tube, for example. An interesting question is: how many cross sectional images of a straight line motion are necessary to be taken in order for the continuous motion to be observed somewhat accurately with discrete images. This would depend it appears on both the angular frequency of the ball around the tube and how nonlinear the forces on the ball are, and of course on the controlled circuit parameters.

Within an article, "Jumping ring experiment: effect of temperature, non-magnetic material and applied current on the jump height," [73] J. Taweeponga, K. Thamaphat, S. Limsuwan writes, "Results of jump height as a function of mass for the copper, aluminum, and brass rings at room and cool temperature for applied voltage of 180, 200, and 220 V are shown in Fig. 4," where here figure one corresponds to graph a) and b) of figure four that Taweeponga et al. describes. One can see that the aluminum conductor was the ring which jumped the highest, and that a higher voltage in the coil which was wound with 2000 turns, the higher the jump height. As one can see in the figure, the temperature dependence produces fairly drastic differences in the jump height. Their coil did have an iron core in it, and this is approximately what my experiment will follow.

The main law which causes the ring to jump is the Faraday-Lenz effect. As current goes through the coil, a current is induced within the ring which acts to move the ring away from the coil. A similar experiment is a single Thompson Ring levitation control experiment. The control ideas would be the same, although the physics principles would be different in why the ring is levitating. The stability criteria, however, would remain the same.

The main interest in my experiment is to stabilize the position of a ferromagnetic material [74]. This is similar to the Thompson Ring Experiments, however, the differential equations will not contain mutual inductance terms [75]. Magnets which I am going to be using are ferromagnetic barring or neodymium magnetic balls [76].

In the presence of a sinusoidally varying magnetic field, I expect the balls to be suspended above the solenoid. Apparently some pistons operate with this action. The current running through the solenoid when it is turned on will cause for a ferromagnetic piston to be pulled into the solenoid. The magnetic field is sinusoidally time dependent which indicates that as the field changes in time, the direction of the magnetic field will change in time [77]. Because the magnetic field changes directions, and the ball has the tendency to align itself in the direction of the magnetic field, one should expect that the magnetic moment [78] of the ball also changes directions along with the field. The net result would be that the ball may spin. Within the tube for my experiment, the ball is constrained, to compensate for the fact that the magnitude of the field in the z direction is all that has been calculated, for the calculations become simplified when removing this degree of freedom with the track constraint. Friction is assumed to be negligible in this case so long as there is not much bumping into the walls of the tube. To make it so the electromagnet only forces the ball in one direction but can be fed a sinusoidal signal, the signal is rectified with a diode bridge rectifier [79].

Bar magnets have an intrinsic magnetic dipole moment because the spins of electrons which create the intrinsic dipole moment for the electron [80] add to create a net field that permeates in the vicinity of the magnet where the usual image is the iron filings surrounding the bar. The magnetic dipole moment of the electron can be seen to exist from experiments like the Stern-Gerlach experiment [81]. In this experiment, the ball can be modeled as a sphere with a tiny ball magnet within it.

Originally, a first, more complicated design was to have two coils with two phases, the initial phase, and the second phase. In the initial phase, coil one is fed the ball with the track, and be design, a switch will activate

the on phase. When phase one is activated by switch, the circuit which controls the voltages within the coils becomes active. Other experiments in which the ball's position is controlled can be performed with such designs. The power supply would have to be much larger than that considered here. Controlling the phase angle of the total magnetic field is made possible by controlling the phase angle of coil two's voltage with respect to coil one's voltage. The voltages produce the desired effective B field. The controller set up in this fashion with voltage amplifiers could be used to control the trajectory of the ball. Of course if different coils or hardware were installed to this simple device, then the study of nonlinear analysis could be performed. Consider connecting these coils, and then different valued power sources which are connected to a second set, a third set, a fourth set, etc... of wires that operate at different frequencies and amplitudes. The study of the nonlinear circuit systems could then be perceived visually as the effect on the ball and the position data. Stability is a major sought criteria for stability is the key for levitation and controlling anything because if you do not stably control the wheel when turning the car wheel, acceleration will not be uniform and you will feel a jerk. The jerk will make it more difficult to control the system. The calculation of the current quantities would be more complicated than in the usual case obviously due to the coupling of one coil within another. The equations of motion of the ball are the same, but the driving circuit is different, so different control information can be extrapolated. For purposes of resources and time, this experiment was simplified into something more achievable but which could show the same effects. My original understanding of the circuit was naïve and overly complicated before learning of the negative feedback techniques which have been developed. As it turns out, this development makes constructing the physical circuit both more efficient physically and financially. Otherwise, many transistors would have to be used to achieve the same gain characteristics.

Amplification and Semiconductor Physics

The study of semiconductor physics [82] produces methods to manufacture chips [83] and small scale electric circuits that form the basis of computation, memory [84], and many modern components. Semiconductor physics is truly the study of solid state physics [85] in general or the study of solids at the molecular and atomic level. Essentially this forms the basis of the informational technology for which we use to handle the informational workloads of the modern life.

The project would most easily be completed if a negative feedback amplifier had an input voltage which is controlled by an Arduino which senses the position of the ball with a laser sensor. A Hall Effect sensor is apparently commonly used in these experiments for measuring the ball's position, however, this experiment utilizes a laser sensor. The semiconductor physics which is of main importance in such a circuit exists within the technologies that are the Arduino, such as the Integrated Circuit Board, which is consistent of many millions of Transistors. Transistors act as an amplifier, and also can be used as a switch depending on whether the voltage across the three terminals respectively allow for the proper Forward and Reverse Bias conditions. There are various different kinds of Transistors such as field effect transistors which use effectively the physical principles but which have variable or different doping densities in addition to different placement and geometries of the p and n material. The MOSFET Transistor, for example, "Microelectronics and Circuit Analysis," by Donald Neaman [86].

Neaman describes the MOSFET in Chapter 3 on page 129 in edition four: "The channel length of a typical integrated circuit MOSFET is less than $1 \mu\text{m}$ (10^{-6} m), which means that MOSFETs are small devices." JFETs are another type of field effect Transistor which can be used for the purpose of amplification. MOSFETs apparently did not come into conception until about the 1970's, where the operational principles of the Bipolar Junction Transistor were developed by William Shockley of Bell Laboratories in 1947. The first diodes operated upon the principles of thermionic emission where Owen Richardson was given the Nobel Prize in 1929 for his investigation of the Thermionic phenomena [87] where the thermal energy given to the cathode is sufficient to overcome the work function which effectively keeps the electrons to the surface of the cathode, which results in the emission of the electrons towards the anode plate. Diodes today are formed by doping two different materials

and joining them together. The semiconductor material is usually Si or Ge and these metals when doped [88] with group 3 material such as Boron yield a structure which has what are called holes because the valence electrons of the surrounding group 4 silicon atoms possess electrons, and ultimately there is a net attraction of the surrounding electrons to the holes due to the relative absence of electrons and respective positive charges where the holes are. The exact opposite of course would happen with the doping of the material with a group 5 element, and this is called an n type material. Bringing these two materials together yields P-N [89] junction by which the operating principles of the modern diode function.

The hole-electron pair [90] was another motivation for the Dark Matter Hypothesis, for the Intrinsic Carrier Concentration of the electrons within the semiconductor that has been doped is:

$$n_i = BT^{\frac{3}{2}} e^{-\frac{E_g}{2kT}} \quad \text{Eq 37)}$$

Where B is a coefficient related to the semiconductor, T is the temperature in Kelvin, E_g is the semiconductor bandgap energy [91], and k is the Boltzmann constant. Obviously holes do not physically exist, however, they have the same numerical quantities which would exist for the electron such as mass and energy. Although the holes are defined analogously to the electrons, the numerical values come out different. From mass energy equivalence, it is easily determined that the mass of a hole is not equal to the mass of an electron although they are defined relatively. Similarly to how complex definitions of the electromagnetic field could show how the hole is relative to the electron, the same can be done with mass. This leads to a pretty interesting hypothesis which is likely testable with further research and data testing.

The Current-Voltage characteristic equation of the Forward Biased diode is:

$$I_D = I_s \left(e^{\frac{V_D}{V_T}} - 1 \right) \quad \text{Eq 38)}$$

Which is known as the Shockley Diode Equation. V_D is the voltage across the diode, and V_T is the thermal voltage which is $V_T = \frac{T}{11,600}$ and μ is a constant usually one. The saturation current. The operation in reverse bias is not the conditions which most diodes are specified for. The reverse bias operation equation for the diode is:

$$I_D = \frac{I_s}{1 - \left(\frac{V_D}{V_B} \right)^n} \quad \text{Eq 39)}$$

The junction also has a capacitance. The amplifier which I am going to use will be connected to an Arduino which has a program to control the voltage, and the amplifier which is consistent of many transistors and tiny circuit elements.

For the following experiment, there is no need to think about the full nature of the physics involved, for it is sufficient to determine the simple differential equations which govern the motion and the functions which describe the magnetic fields. In this case, as it appears from a majority of cases in Electrodynamics, will not be complex components to consider, although they do assist in forming solutions to the differential equations. Usually a waveform may be written as a field with a real and imaginary part where the imaginary part is truncated after the solution is obtained.

The experiment has been designed so that there is a B field along an axis which a magnetic object that possesses a magnetic dipole. I assume here that the B field will torque the ball to align the magnetic dipole moment in the direction of the field much like the needle of a compass does in the presence of Earth's magnetic field. By constraining the axis that the ball can move along, the problem of the ball jumping around chaotically within the acceleration tube is minimized. Once the field initially aligns the magnetic moment, we should expect it to remain aligned because as the magnetic field moves, the ball will rotate. From conservation we should expect that the

rotation occurs in unison with the field. It is for this reason that I expect to see the ball's magnetic moment align itself with the direction of the field and be forced by the field. Newton's Equations for the ball is simply:

$$m \frac{d^2y(t)}{dt^2} = F_B - mg \quad \text{Eq 40}$$

Where, F_B is the magnetic force acting on the ball, y is the coordinate along the axis, m the mass of the ball, and g the acceleration of the ball. One only needs to consider the forces in the y direction due to the constraint which is the guiding tube or acceleration chamber. The forces on the ball depend on the molecular structure of the ball.

From Griffiths, *pg* 268, the force on a magnetic dipole in a magnetic field is (I use z as opposed to y for notational consistency) [92]:

$$F_B = \nabla(M \cdot B_T) = K \frac{\partial B_T(x, y, z, t)}{\partial z(t)} \hat{z} \quad \text{Eq 41}$$

Which is also the case for the Stern-Gerlach experiment which shows that the electron has a magnetic dipole moment by the passing of a cathode beam through a magnetic field. As the electron's dipole passes through the magnetic field which possesses a vertical gradient, we see that the electron is deflected in the vertical. This experiment is similar, and the crucial fact for alignment in this experiment is the freedom of the ball to rotate.

The magnetic field, B_T is the sum of the fields, B_T . Due to the fact that the magnetic field is voltage dependent, and we are able to control the phase between the two fields, we can by result control the trajectory of the ball by controlling the voltage across the coils because the voltage controls the current. Additionally, by sensing where the ball is at within the coil system, we know how strong the Magnetic field and therefore voltage has to be to control the position of the ball due to the fact that the magnetic field is a function of the current going through the wires. The voltage controller will allow for us to control the current.

The E.O.M is:

$$m \frac{d^2y(t)}{dt^2} = \frac{-\partial(M \cdot B_1(y, t))}{\partial y} - mg \quad \text{Eq 42}$$

How do changes in the wire geometry results in changes on what the circuit has to do to control the differential equation? The stability conditions are the derived in the same manner, however, we should expect that the ball is stabilized in different places for the different wire geometries because the forces will be different. Studying the effect of different wire geometries tells one how the differential equation is dependent on the wire geometries. Due to the fact that the magnetic field is controlled by the voltage and the voltage is controlled by the Arduino which is sensing the velocity and position of the ball, the magnetic field is therefore dependent on the velocity and position of the ball.

Another way to get this equation is by the force on the ball from the coil being given by:

$$\overrightarrow{F_{dipole}} = (\vec{m} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B} \quad \text{Eq 43}$$

Where this gives the newton differential equation as:

$$m\vec{a} = \overrightarrow{F_{dipole}} - mg \quad \text{Eq 44}$$

Or

$$m \frac{d\vec{v}}{dt} = (\vec{m} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B} - mg\hat{y} \quad \text{Eq 45}$$

But if we ignore the fringing at the edges of the cylinder and the magnetic fields to the left and right of the cylinder and only select the part of the field that will be affecting the ball, if the force of gravity acts along y

axis, then it is safe to state that $\frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial z} = 0$, and this would imply that $m_x = m_z = 0$ so that all of the magnetic moment is in the direction of the magnetic field which is along the y axis which would make the magnetic moment $m_y = |m|$. In the most general case it may not be possible to ignore the fluid interaction with the ball but if we ignore air resistance the torque $\tau = \vec{m} \times \vec{B}$ aligns the ball with the field. In general cases there will be a spin of the ball introduced from the interaction with the field. I am not sure if this is correct but it seems that $m = i_{dipole} NA$. The sphere- coil interaction has an equal and opposite interaction so there is not only the forces on the ball but also the forces on the coil if we are being more precise but in this experiment the forces on the coil are eliminated by securing the coil to the apparatus.

Then the magnetic field can be plotted as a function of the current distribution in 3 space by the Biot Savart law:

$$d\vec{B} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \left(\frac{d\vec{s} \times \vec{r}}{r^3} \right) \quad \text{Eq 46}$$

Where \vec{r} is the vector for the direction of the current. Since $i = \frac{dq}{dt}$ the force then is given by the Lorentz force law:

$$\vec{F} = q\vec{v} \times \vec{B} = i\vec{dr} \times \vec{B} \quad \text{Eq 47}$$

The magnetic field within the solenoid is given by Equation 29-23) Jearl Walker “Fundamentals of Physics,” page 850 [93],

$$B = \mu_0 ni \quad \text{Eq 48}$$

Which is constant with respect to the spatial derivatives, which indicates that within the solenoid, there should be no magnetic force on the ball. The magnetic field above the coil can be found with the Biot-Savart Law. Jearl Walker, chapter 29, page 852 [94], the magnitude of the magnetic field above a single current carrying loop is given by:

$$B(z) = \frac{\mu_0 i R^2}{2(R^2 + z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad \text{Eq 49}$$

This magnetic field can also be written in the form which recognizes the magnetic dipole moment of the circular loop. If geometry of the coil is not cylindrical but is created by winding the coil around a core with circular loops then the radius would be a function of the height, y: $R \rightarrow R(y)$, then:

$$B(y) = \int \frac{\mu_0 i N \left(\frac{L(y)}{2} \right)^2 dy}{2 \left(\left(\frac{L(y)}{2} \right)^2 + y^2 \right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad \text{Eq 50}$$

In the general case:

$$m \frac{d^2 \vec{r}}{dt^2} = (\vec{m} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B} - mg\hat{y} \quad \text{Eq 51}$$

And the stability conditions have $\frac{d^2 \vec{r}}{dt^2} = 0$ which makes the above equation become:

$$(\vec{m} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B} = mg\hat{y} \quad \text{Eq 52}$$

Which with the above magnetic field equation inserted here gives:

Eq 53)

$$|m| \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\int \frac{\mu_0 i N \left(\frac{L(y)}{2} \right)^2 dy}{2 \left(\left(\frac{L(y)}{2} \right)^2 + y^2 \right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) = mg \hat{y}$$

I think this would be for the case with the diamagnetic material where the induced current within the material is proportional to the current on the coils. It would give the same equation. I do not see however how we can be justified in defining the magnetic moment of our material unless it is diamagnetic to have a electric current from intrinsic electron dynamics/spin which has an induced current proportional to the current on the coil. Nonetheless to make more progress we move on from this point assuming it is done elsewhere in literature but the equation will take this general form whichever we use where there is a partial derivative on the magnetic field. This is because in the general case the magnetic moment might not align with the field and there will be a magnetic moment that has a direction which is dependent on the field strength since there will be a torque force on the ball.

Circuit Design

For a constant K which has to be measured because the material specifications are not given such as for the different windings.

The path of calculating the geometry explicitly would require precisely calculating the integral or summing the terms. Apparently, an easier way of performing the calculations has been performed by modeling the coil as an inductor which is a function of the axis.

The position of the ball will be sensed from a photo sensor. The photo sensor will have a small output voltage which is amplified so that the circuit can interpret in terms of voltage what the position of the ball means. The stability of the ball therefore is translated into the question of the stability of the circuit which can be interpreted with the transfer function which can be interpreted with Bode and Nyquist plots. The Laplace Transformation of the differential equation yields a function of s which is added in series with the control circuit.

Magnetic levitation experiments which are almost identical to that described here have been performed such as in the article, “Magnetic Levitation Testbed for Controls Education,” Kevin Craig, Thomas Kurfess, and Mark Nagurka [95], where such as in Craig et al.’s experiment, the magnitude of the force which can be interpreted as a voltage which acts to balance the differential equation that describes the physical phenomena is found by looking at the force as a function of the coil’s inductance for the reason that the magnetic field is a function of the inductance and current:

$$f(x, i) = -\frac{i^2}{2} \left(\frac{d}{dx} L(x) \right); L = L_1 + \frac{L_0 x_0}{x} \text{ so } f(x) = -\frac{Ci^2}{2x^2} \quad \text{Eq 54)}$$

Where they modeled the sensor as “a simple gain element,” where $v_s = k_s z$ and C is a constant to be determined. The author of this image for the operational amplifier is: N. F. Macia “A Method for Obtaining the Transfer Function of Inverting and Non-inverting Op-amp Circuits Based on Classical Feedback Theory” [96].

Apparently the linearized force is best approximated with equation four from Nagurka’s article which uses the inductance model to achieve a force function and uses the voltage function to create the transfer function. The linearized force equation can be obtained by performing a Taylor Expansion of the force the inductance has to be measured. Notice how the denominator again, such as in Yoon’s paper has a cubic term in s. The stability location is given by equation 4):

$$\frac{Ci^2}{2x^2} = mg \quad \text{Eq 55)}$$

Figure 34 [*34]: Design of Circuit for Physical Device:

There is an error terms from the hall effect sensor not being exactly at the edge of the electromagnet and being within the electromagnet. Using a washer and clipping the washer and placing a penny on ends of the washers as caps to protect the hall effect sensor from the ball smashing it and so that the hall effect sensor can get a reading on the voltage induced by the electromagnet at the top essentially away from the ball and at the bottom which would measure the field of the magnet plus the ball. In the more general scenario it may be necessary to place sensors within the ball for complete control.

Figure 35 [*35]: 1d Mag Lev Circuit

This is the common base configuration of the circuit with $v_{out} = \beta v_{in}$ with β the gain factor from the transistor. The current drawn to the inductor (pull coil) is given by the laplace transformation of the governing differential equation. The kirchoff loop can be drawn through the transistor and pull coil and battery to give:

$$V_{batt} + .7V - V_{RL} - V_L = V_{out} \quad \text{Eq 56)$$

With $V_L = \frac{Ldi}{dt}$ this produces the differential equation:

$$V_{batt} + .7V - i_L R_L - L \frac{di_L}{dt} = V_{out} \quad \text{Eq 57)}$$

Using $v_{out} = \beta v_{in}$ and $i_{in} = \frac{V_{in} - V_{\#5}}{R_1}$ we can control the values for the RHS of the equation:

$$V_{in} = i_{in} R_1 + V_{\#5} \quad \text{Eq 58)}$$

$$V_{batt} + .7V - i_L R_L - L \frac{di_L}{dt} = V_{out} = \beta v_{in} = \beta (i_{in} R_1 + V_{\#5}) \quad \text{Eq 59)}$$

This equation shows the current and therefore the magnetic field of the field inducer is controlled by the voltage on pin #1, $V_{\#1}$ terms. There will be a small leakage current from the transistor. The s domain transformation of the voltage equation gives the ability to define the transfer function. The transfer function for the circuit can be plotted from here. It is clear that $V_{\#1}$ can be made a function of the magnetic field by relating this circuit equation to the magnetic field with separating the current from the newton equation. The inverse statement is true that the magnetic field can be plotted as a function of the voltage function on pin #1. The magnetic field then can be plotted as a function of the voltage on digital pin #1 by i_L being inserted for $B(x, i)$. we can inpt then various voltage functions for the coil and observe the field. The ball also can be controlled on different paths by choosing conditions different than the stability conditions.

The fields can be plotted from the coil real time by inserting hall instruments in newton differential equation real time and using the ai to solve the equations with the partial data or initial conditions real time. We also can plot the force field functions as a function of Arduino pin voltage as well. We can then plot the newton differential equation as a function of the Arduino pin voltage. If we want to make other magnetic fields and different magnetic feld control technologies we would need more coils and to remove the conditions that $\ddot{x} = 0$ and allow other trajectories to exist.

Apparently the PID algorithm is sufficient enough to make the approximation of the Arduino pin voltage with the error function: $e(t) = -v_{current}(t) + v_{setpoint}(t)$ but this needs to be double checked.

$$v_{\#1} = k_p + k_d \left(\frac{de}{dt} \right) + k_i \int edt \quad \text{Eq 60)}$$

Where the proportional gain factors are given by the k_p k_d and k_i constants. It seems that some lemma or theorem can be made for how the Laplace transform of the newton differential equation is related to the Laplace transform of the circuit equation n and what exactly the error function is.

Figure 36 [*36]

Figure 37 [*37]

The circuit design has a number of components. I have purchased a small electronics kit from Amazon. There are many other variations of this project online and this is not really that unique and mostly for visual addition of the mathematical model discussed here. The circuit components are: potentiometers, a laser position sensor, resistors, capacitors, variable capacitors, a bread board, an Arduino, an operational amplifier, wire for the coil, an iron core and some of the physical components are: a neodymium magnet, a plastic control tube, a small plastic stand held together with basic plastic glue.

I also used other various components for the various Arduino experiments I performed with the kits I bought from Amazon and the sensors I bought from adafruit and other online vendors.

Figure 38 [*38]

Cost

I bought the cheapest components altogether which were on sale during the day that I put in the order, which included a small electronics kit, a small potentiometer kit, and the Arduino Uno, sensors, etc. Some research articles indicate that the products altogether cost less than 50 dollars, which is nowhere close to what I would tell students that the actual price for constructing a magnetic levitation device like this at home, for an engineering project. The following chart shows all of the product I have purchased, including the prices. The above tools including the TI-84 calculator, vice-grips, tape measure and laptop were mine which I had previously purchased, and without the laptop, and these tools which I owned, the price of a project like this would be considerably higher. Many of the research articles on similar projects do not take the time to investigate the magnetic field from the different windings, and this due to the fact that a quality EMF detector is not a household item, of course added to the cost. In general, the more measurements of different types that are required, the more costly the experiment will be. The kits were purchased with the assumption that all of the material is reusable for other projects, so that the one time purchase would be able to suffice the needs of later projects. Even with being able to use a portable Oscilloscope which connects to the computer from Cleveland State University which saves the cost of oscilloscopes which are usually expensive, the cost of the experiment was realistically speaking more than \$100, and if you are a student with no tools or a laptop, the project would cost more realistically probably \$800-\$1500 depending on the quality of the oscilloscope and the laptop purchased. Now of course, this experiment made many different measurements and variations which are not usually done with the proof of concept videos with a steel screw as the iron core, for example. Good, safe practice for the design of control systems obviously requires more flexibility, and by having a few different sized components, and more flexibility, various different circuits, and magnetic levitation experiments can be designed with these parts. In general the prices of the components are the same, however, what use are these specific components for other circuits later on, if for

example only exactly the circuit components used were purchased? At some point, creativity becomes limited by the resources available.

A sketch with the parts list can be seen in the following image:

The part numbers correspond to the sketched image above:

Item	Cost	Size	Part Number	Specifications
Plywood	~\$5.00	(2 ft x 4ft) (Needs cut down for stand)	P1	Interior use plywood
Wire for Levitation Coil (Magnet Wire)	\$10.35	250 feet	P2	Gauge: 22 AWG Weight: 8.0 ounces
Soft Iron Rod.	\$14.50	(0.5 dia X 6 long) inches	P3	Ideal Core for making electromagnets.
Neodymium Magnetic Balls	\$11.50	Diameter 1: 15.88mm D2: 19.05mm D3: 6mm	P4	Chrome Plated Neodymium Sphere Magnets; N40 and N45 rare Earth Metals
Plastic stand	\$1.00	Approx. 13 cm x 13 cm	P5	--
Plastic Ring (for holding electromagnet to stand)	Came from P9, \$0.00	.5 in tall, 3.5cm OD, 2.8cm ID	P6	Use Utility Knife to cut from P9.
Super Glue (fixing apparatus)	~5.00	--	P7	--
Saw (for cutting wood)	Owned	--	P8	--
Hollow, clear plastic cylinder (for stand)	~\$2.00	60cm length, 3.5cm OD, 2.8cm ID	P9	--
Circular Clamp One	~\$.50	Variable diameter	P10	--
Circular Clamp Two	~\$.50	Variable diameter	P11	--
Flat L bracket	~ \$2.50	4 in x 4 in	P12	--
VL6180X Time of Flight Distance Sensor	\$13.95	2cm x 1.5cm x 5cm	P13	
Arduino Uno	\$13.98	7 cm x 5 cm x 3 cm	P14	1) ATmega328P microcontroller 2) Input voltage - 7-12V 3) 5V Electric current: 500MA

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4) 3.3V Electric current: 50MA 5) 14 Digital I/O Pins (6 PWM outputs) 6) 8 Analog Inputs 7) 32k Flash Memory 8) 16Mhz Clock Speed
Arduino Number Two	\$13.98	7 cm x 5 cm x 3 cm	P15	--
Computer		Laptop	P16	Dell Inspiron
Texas Instruments LM358N LM358 Dual Operational Amplifier DIP8	\$1.00 per unit (only need one)	.75 cm x 1 cm x 1cm	P17	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of Channels: 2 • Common Mode Rejection Ratio (Min): 65 dB • Input Offset Voltage: 7 mV • Input Bias Current (Max): 250 nA • Slew Rate: 0.3 V/us
Capacitor Bank and variable capacitors	Came with kit	Less than an inch	P18	50 microFarad, 100 microFarad, 40 microFarad max variable capacitors
Resistive component and Potentiometers	Came with kit	Less than an inch	P19	--
Diode Bridge Rectifier	Came With kit		P20	--
Breadboard	Came with kit	16.5 cm x 5.5 cm	P21	18 V
Wires/Connectors	Came with kit	--	P22	--
Ohm Meter	Owned \$0.00		P23	Woods AMMW1 Analog Multimeter
Thermistor (for temperature reading of coil)	Came with kit	Less than an inch	P24	--
Laser Temperature Sensor	Owned	Hand held	P25	Non contact IR thermometer. Thermal Readings from laser - 22 to 700 degrees.
Battery Holder One	\$4.00	13.5cm x 7 cm	P26	--

Battery Holder Two	\$4.00	13.5cm x 7 cm	P26	--
Screwdriver	Owned	--	P28	--
Electromagnetic Field Tester	\$18.00	4 cm x 13 cm x 2.5 cm	P29	1) Max Range: 1999 mili Gauss, 199 micro Tesla 2) Resolution: .01 μ T, .01mG 3) Band width: 30 Hz to 300 Hz 4) Accuracy: \pm 5% at 60 Hz.
Electronics Kit	\$18.00	12.2 Ounces	P30	--
Potentiometer and Variable Resistor Package	\$15.00	--	P31	--
Batteries (D Cell)	\$10.00	--	P32	8 pack for powering Op-Amp

By buying the arduino kit and these tools I got to play around with other Arduino experiments as well as I bought motors and small transformers as well as oscilloscopes to test the circuits and power amplifiers that I resold after getting the use I wanted to and testing this at home. I also got to learn about the control systems for the toy autonomous cars and autonomous things in general from other tangents in this project. I got to use many different sensors for the Arduino kit and if I recall properly I have used almost every sensor type and or researched them all as well. Usual cutting tools for cutting wire would help but is not needed with the wire kit.

Total Number of Parts/Tools	Total Cost of Project	Weight
32	\$150.81 (Includes many different variations of experiment and utilities for basic circuit design)	More than a pound

Comparing this price to the \$20 bucks online for some of the more basic magnetic levitation circuits seems to be within range of what would be expected. If one had access to an oscilloscope or the other components already around the house or facility such as batteries, resistors, capacitors, etc, then this project could be significantly less expensive, however, if you are starting from scratch, and have almost none of the parts, you will probably spend about this much at least if you want accurate measurements, to test other variations of the experiment which are not attainable with a basic design. Being able to run the Arduino program on my computer for the oscilloscope, for example, saved me probably about \$150 + because quality oscilloscopes can be expensive. There are various other magnetic levitator toys and devices which can be bought as well that show the circuits and everything so nothing really new.

Because the plotting program I was forced to use did not have the ability to run the Arduino program as a test run, I instead looked at the magnetic levitator circuit for different inputs and looked at the response without the Arduino's correction. The circuit diagram is pictured below:

The stability locations for the current are given from:

$$\frac{Li^2}{2x^2} = mg \quad \text{Eq 61)}$$

The inductance is approximated with:

$$L = \frac{N^2 \mu k A}{l} \quad \text{Eq 62)}$$

The relative permeability for iron is $k = 200000$, the length of the wrapping is $l = .1651$ m, $N = 1120$, and the $A = 7.06 \text{ E-4 m}^2$. For Winding # 1, this gives the inductance for the coil # 1 to be: $L \approx 1350 \text{ H}$.

The largest balls mass is approximately $m = .03\text{kg}$. This gives a way to model the current which needs to be adjusted to reach the stability location. The equation with these numbers becomes:

$$47.9105i = x.$$

As one can see, the stability condition is dependent on how much current is going through the wire, or the voltage induced.

Using the same Neodymium Magnet with mass .03 kg, at .127 meters, the ball is completely taken by the iron core's pull, which indicates that past this height at minimum strength, the system will be unstable because it will be pulled into the solenoid.

On the other side, with maximum current flowing through the wire, which is known because the maximum voltage 6V as is set by the power rails for the operational amplifier and because the resistance is approximately 10k Ohm, the current and which I approximate to be: .0288 m, which is 1.13 inches from the bottom of the stand, which is not too bad a guess as it fits within the box, and is in-between the magnet and the sensor. My original idea was to measure the inductance with an oscilloscope, but last minute, with COVID-19, this became a challenge. I tried to use the Arduino Oscilloscope, but the readings when I hooked up, were too unreliable unfortunately. Additionally, the second part of the experiment which will have to be done at a later time, called for a magnetic field intensity detector. I purchased the magnetic field intensity detector, and as one might expect, you get what you pay for, and my measurements were not accurate with the cheap detector I bought. As one could imagine, the crisis has impacted this project quite a bit.

In this circuit the current is the control variable.

Software

1-D Arduino Code with Two Hall effect sensors:

This Arduino code defines a control system for a levitator using Hall effect sensors and a Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller. The levitator consists of two Hall sensors (topHallPin and bottomHallPin) that measure the magnetic field intensity. These readings are used to calculate an error term, representing the difference between the two sensor values.

The PID controller is implemented with the parameters Kp (proportional gain), Ki (integral gain), and Kd (derivative gain). The levitation setpoint is the desired magnetic field intensity, and the controller adjusts the levitation point by manipulating an output signal applied to the controlPin (connected to an actuator or electromagnet). The PID algorithm helps maintain the system at the desired setpoint by considering the current error, integral of past errors, and the rate of change of the error.

The setup function initializes the system, configuring pins and printing a startup message to the serial monitor. In the loop function, the Hall sensor values are read, and the PID algorithm is applied to generate an output for the controlPin. The levitation setpoint can be manually adjusted using two buttons (addPin and subPin). The value_log function logs the Hall sensor values and the current setpoint to the serial monitor. The entire loop continuously runs, regulating the levitation system based on sensor feedback and user input.

The code for the 1d Levitator is:

```
// Define Hall sensor pins  
int topHallPin = A0; // Analogic Hall Sensor at the top  
int bottomHallPin = A1; // Analogic Hall Sensor at the bottom  
  
// Define control pin  
int controlPin = 9; // Arduino Digital Pin 9  
  
// Define other digital pins  
int subPin = 7; // Arduino Digital Pin 7;  
int addPin = 8; // Arduino Digital Pin 8;  
  
// Define PID parameters  
double setpoint = 228.0; // Levitation Point Value  
double input, output, lastInput = 0;  
double Kp = 2.0; // Proportional gain  
double Ki = 5.0; // Integral gain  
double Kd = 1.0; // Derivative gain  
double integral = 0;  
  
void setup() {  
    // Levitator initialization Begin;  
    Serial.begin(57600);  
    Serial.println("Levitator by JSyA");  
    Serial.println("Starting...");  
  
    // Digital Pins Work Mode Setup;  
    pinMode(controlPin, OUTPUT);  
    pinMode(subPin, INPUT_PULLUP);  
    pinMode(addPin, INPUT_PULLUP);
```

```
// Levitator initialization End;  
Serial.println("Started.");  
}  
  
void loop() {  
    // Hall Sensor Read (Magnetic Field Intensity);  
    int topHallVal = analogRead(topHallPin);  
    int bottomHallVal = analogRead(bottomHallPin);  
  
    // Calculate the error term between the two sensors  
    input = topHallVal - bottomHallVal;  
  
    // Compute PID  
    double error = setpoint - input;  
    integral += error;  
    output = Kp * error + Ki * integral + Kd * (input - lastInput);  
  
    // Apply PID output to control pin  
    digitalWrite(controlPin, output > 0 ? HIGH : LOW);  
  
    lastInput = input;  
  
    // Increase The Value Of Levitation Point;  
    if (digitalRead(addPin) == LOW) {  
        setpoint++;  
        value_log();  
        delay(250);  
    }  
  
    // Decrease The Value Of Levitation Point;  
    if (digitalRead(subPin) == LOW) {
```

```

    setpoint--;
    value_log();
    delay(250);
}

// Log values
value_log();
delay(250);
}

void value_log() {
    // Show the Hall Sensor Values;
    Serial.print("TopHall=[");
    Serial.print(analogRead(topHallPin));
    Serial.print("], BottomHall=[");
    Serial.print(analogRead(bottomHallPin));
    Serial.print("], ");

    // Show the Levitation Point Value;
    Serial.print("Setpoint=[");
    Serial.print(setpoint);
    Serial.println("];");
}

```

Tuning the PID (Proportional, Integral, Derivative) controller involves finding appropriate values for the Kp (Proportional), Ki (Integral), and Kd (Derivative) parameters to achieve the desired system performance. The tuning process is often iterative and involves experimenting to find a set of parameters that provide stable and responsive control. Here's a general approach to tuning PID parameters:

1. Start with Default Values:

Set Kp, Ki, and Kd to zero initially.

Increase Kp until you get a fast response but be cautious of overshooting.

2. Proportional (P) Tuning:

Increase K_p until the system begins to oscillate.

If the response is too slow, increase K_p .

If the system becomes unstable with too much overshooting, reduce K_p .

3. Integral (I) Tuning:

Introduce K_i to eliminate steady-state error (residual error in a constant system).

Start with a small K_i value and increase it until the steady-state error is eliminated.

Be cautious, as a high K_i can introduce overshooting and instability.

4. Derivative (D) Tuning:

Introduce K_d to improve system damping and reduce overshooting.

Start with a small K_d and increase it until oscillations are minimized.

Too much K_d can lead to an excessively damped response.

5. Fine-Tuning:

Iteratively adjust K_p , K_i , and K_d to balance performance metrics (rise time, overshoot, settling time).

Use trial and error while observing the system response and adjusting parameters accordingly.

Utilize advanced tuning methods like Ziegler-Nichols or other optimization techniques if needed.

6. Test Under Various Conditions:

Validate the tuned parameters under different operating conditions.

Check for robustness and responsiveness to disturbances.

7. Consider System Characteristics:

Understand the dynamics of your specific system and how changes in each parameter affect the overall performance.

8. Use Simulation Tools:

If possible, use simulation tools to model the system and predict the effects of different parameter values.

9. Iterate as Needed:

Continue refining the parameters based on real-world performance until the desired balance is achieved.

Remember that PID tuning is not a one-size-fits-all process; it depends on the specific characteristics and requirements of your control system. It often involves a balance between achieving a fast response and avoiding overshooting or instability. Practical experience and observation of the system's behavior are crucial during the tuning process.

The values we should get for the tuning parameters here should be the same as those predicted by the transfer function.

3d version of the code:

This Arduino code is designed to control a levitator system with multiple coils using Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) control. The system consists of five coils, each equipped with two Hall sensors positioned at the top and bottom. These Hall sensors measure the magnetic field intensity, and the difference between the top and bottom sensor readings is used as an input for the PID controller.

The code defines constants such as the number of coils (`numCoils`) and the number of sensors per coil (`numSensorsPerCoil`). It also specifies the pins for the Hall sensors (`hallPins`) and the control pins (`controlPins`). The PID parameters (proportional, integral, and derivative gains) and setpoints are declared for each coil.

In the `setup()` function, the system is initialized by configuring the control pins as outputs and initiating the serial communication for debugging.

The `loop()` function continuously reads the Hall sensor values for each coil, calculates the error term between the setpoint and the actual input, applies the PID control algorithm separately for each coil, and adjusts the control signals for the coils accordingly. The system state is logged to the serial monitor using the `value_log()` function, which displays the Hall sensor values, setpoints, and coil indices.

This code provides a modular approach to controlling multiple coils in a levitator system, allowing for individualized PID parameters and setpoints for each coil. The PID control helps maintain the magnetic levitation at the desired setpoint for each coil.

```
// Define constants
```

```
const int numCoils = 5;
```

```
const int numSensorsPerCoil = 2;
```

```
// Define sensor pins
```

```
int hallPins[numCoils][numSensorsPerCoil] = {
```

```
  {A0, A1}, // Coil 1: Hall sensors at the top and bottom
```

```
  {A2, A3}, // Coil 2
```

```
  {A4, A5}, // Coil 3
```

```
  {A6, A7}, // Coil 4
```

```
  {A8, A9} // Coil 5
```

```
};
```

```
// Define control pins
```

```
int controlPins[numCoils] = {9, 10, 11, 12, 13}; // Arduino Digital Pins 9-13
```

```
// Define PID parameters
```

```

double setpoints[numCoils] = {228.0, 228.0, 228.0, 228.0, 228.0};
double inputs[numCoils], outputs[numCoils];
double Kp[numCoils] = {2.0, 2.0, 2.0, 2.0, 2.0};
double Ki[numCoils] = {5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0, 5.0};
double Kd[numCoils] = {1.0, 1.0, 1.0, 1.0, 1.0};
double integral[numCoils] = {0};
double lastError[numCoils] = {0};

void setup() {
    // Levitator initialization Begin;
    Serial.begin(57600);
    Serial.println("Levitator by JSyA");
    Serial.println("Starting...");

    // Digital Pins Work Mode Setup;
    for (int i = 0; i < numCoils; i++) {
        pinMode(controlPins[i], OUTPUT);
    }

    // Levitator initialization End;
    Serial.println("Started.");
}

void loop() {
    // Read Hall Sensor values for each coil
    for (int i = 0; i < numCoils; i++) {
        inputs[i] = analogRead(hallPins[i][0]) - analogRead(hallPins[i][1]);
    }

    // Apply PID control for each coil
    for (int i = 0; i < numCoils; i++) {

```

```

double error = setpoints[i] - inputs[i];
integral[i] += error;
double derivative = error - lastError[i];

outputs[i] = Kp[i] * error + Ki[i] * integral[i] + Kd[i] * derivative;

// Apply PID output to control pin
digitalWrite(controlPins[i], outputs[i] > 0 ? HIGH : LOW);

lastError[i] = error;
}

// Log values
value_log();
delay(250);
}

void value_log() {
// Show the Hall Sensor Values for each coil
for (int i = 0; i < numCoils; i++) {
Serial.print("Coil ");
Serial.print(i + 1);
Serial.print(": TopHall=[");
Serial.print(analogRead(hallPins[i][0]));
Serial.print("], BottomHall=[");
Serial.print(analogRead(hallPins[i][1]));
Serial.print("], Setpoint=[");
Serial.print(setpoints[i]);
Serial.println("];");
}
}

```

Real time 3d plotting of the magnetic field

While the Arduino program is running and properly connected to the apparatus, open Spyder IDE. This Python script uses the Matplotlib library to create a real-time 3D quiver plot based on data received from a serial port. It assumes that the serial data follows a specific format, with lines starting with "SensorData" and containing comma-separated numerical values representing a vector in 3D space.

The script establishes a serial connection with a specified port (COM3 in this case) at a baud rate of 57600. It then initializes a 3D plot using Matplotlib, setting up an initial quiver plot with arbitrary data. The quiver plot is a representation of vectors in 3D space, and in this case, it serves as a dynamic visualization of the incoming sensor data.

Inside the main loop, the script continuously reads lines from the serial port. When it encounters a line starting with "SensorData," it extracts the numerical values, updates the quiver plot with the new data, and redraws the plot to reflect the changes. This creates a real-time visualization of the changing vectors.

The script includes exception handling to ensure a clean exit. If the user interrupts the script (e.g., using a keyboard interrupt), it closes the serial port and the plot. Any other exceptions are caught, and an error message is printed.

Finally, the script closes the serial port when it's done. This code is particularly useful for visualizing dynamic data, such as sensor readings, in a real-time and interactive manner using Matplotlib.

Here is the python code to be run while the Arduino code is running:

```
import serial

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

from mpl_toolkits.mplot3d import Axes3D

# Adjust the serial port name accordingly
ser = serial.Serial('COM3', 57600, timeout=1)

fig = plt.figure()
ax = fig.add_subplot(111, projection='3d')

# Set up initial quiver plot with arbitrary data
quiver = ax.quiver(0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, length=50, normalize=True, color='r')

plt.show(block=False)
```

```

try:
    while True:
        line = ser.readline().decode('utf-8').strip()
        if line.startswith("SensorData"):
            data = [int(x) for x in line.split(',')[1:]]

            # Update quiver plot with new data
            quiver.remove()

            quiver = ax.quiver(data[0], data[1], data[2], data[3], data[4], data[5], data[6], data[7], data[8],
data[9], length=50, normalize=True, color='r')

            # Redraw the plot
            fig.canvas.draw()
            fig.canvas.flush_events()

except KeyboardInterrupt:
    ser.close()
    plt.close()

except Exception as e:
    print(f"Error: {e}")

# Close the serial port when done
ser.close()

```

Differential Geometric Relation to Complex Number Theory for nonlinear Control Theory Analysis

Comparing the two functions simultaneously (RZTF and RZTF') allow for information about the definition of the functions including the zeros to be understood. One thing you might have considered before, is: what if the units were physically measured with imaginary rods? Then, the magnitude of the Transfer Function would be the root of a difference of squares. This is the signature of the hyperbolic geometry for Special Relativity. This, and the connection to nonlinear control theory and control theory itself is really the consideration of general compensators which are rational complex functions. Notice, how that as opposed to the definition that the circular Cartesian geometry which results from real legs, compared to the hyperbolic geometry which results from the single sign difference for the definition of the magnitude of the Transfer function. It is like asking what the transfer function looks like from the perspective of a creature who only perceives complex numbers? The definitions are relative to the coordinate system.

The general mechanism for loop shaping would require a general method for modeling zeros and poles of the function, and the way which seems most viable is the stability criteria necessary for the oscillations to occur. For the values of the minima to go from negative to positive, and the maxima to likewise go from positive to negative over and over, due to the extreme value theorem, zeros occur in between these sign oscillations. For a complex function, zeros would likewise show the sign swapping character. A numerical map of the function and its derivatives using the same experiment shows how the function evolves in time, and how the continuity equations imply that symmetry only exists in a few places, specifically for the Riemann Zeta Function.

In general, the nonlinear case is obviously more complicated than the linear case because the idea of flatness can no longer be applied. How then could one obtain stability in a case which is highly unstable? The easiest way I see which would be best accomplishable is to work backwards because the solution of the differential equation will be unknown.

The viewing of the RZF as a sum of phasor operations as opposed to a sum of two continuous complex surfaces certainly yields different interpretations of the same physical data. The phasor interpretation allows for the same model to be interpreted in such a way as to analyze the systems properties in general. The method is simple, however it certainly requires understanding the components of it to operate it which is what makes it inherently difficult.

Where the coordinate transformation which describes the circuit is:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= a \cosh(u) \cos(v) \\ y &= a \sinh(u) \sin(v) \end{aligned} \tag{Eq 63}$$

Notice that a single minus sign in front of the coefficients makes for the function to be completely different, either circular or elliptical coordinates depending on the sign. The same is true of the coordinates that describe space-time in special relativity for a 1-D spatial consideration. Constructing these systems all with the same Pythagorean Theorem rule, the distances in the coordinate systems can be visualized:

Cartesian	$d\vec{r} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} dx \\ dt \end{pmatrix}$	$dr = \sqrt{dx^2 + dy^2}$
Relativity/Lorentz	$d\vec{s} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} dx \\ icdt \end{pmatrix}$	$ds = \sqrt{dx^2 - c^2 dt^2}$
Elliptical Coordinates	$d\vec{r} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} h_u du \\ h_v dv \end{pmatrix}$	$dr = \sqrt{h_u^2 du^2 + h_v^2 dv^2}$
Magnitude of Transfer Function:	$H = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Re(H) \\ i(Im(H)) \end{pmatrix}$	$H = \sqrt{Re(H)^2 + Im(H)^2}$

Consider a general nonlinear magnetic levitation system with many coils and inductive terms, along with complicated amplifier circuits and acceleration terms, and ultimately one considers a more general algebraic set of equations which describes the phenomena. The differential equation which describes the position of the ball would also be a more complicated differential equation because the action on the ball is highly dependent upon the different wire geometries, sizes, connections and physical location of the devices. One would ultimately obtain, in generality, an s domain function which represents the circuit, however, to sustain the analogy, there has to be an imaginary energy which balances the differential equation. The network and position of the ball in general, is then a very complicated algebraic equation in the s domain with N terms:

The circuit function is:

$$H(s) = \sum_{n=1}^N h_n(s) \quad \text{Eq 64)}$$

And the output of the function would also be a sum of N terms for reasons of symmetry:

$$Y(s) = \sum_{n=1}^N y_n(s). \quad \text{Eq 65)}$$

The fact that $H(s)$ can be written as a phasor with a positive magnitude with an angle with respect to the axis of the complex plane, indicates that the output and the individual output terms should be considered to be phasors in the complex domain, so that the sum of all the phasors produces the outputs.

Now that we know that by taking the Laplace transform and in other general cases other integral transforms of the differential equations for the circuit phenomena and the physics phenomena of the interaction between coil and magnetic ball we can understand the events in the s domain and other domains from integral transforms. Summarizing:

$$\text{Laplace(Newton Differential Equation (t))} \rightarrow \text{Newton Differential Equation (s)} \quad \text{Eq 66)}$$

$$\text{Laplace(Circuit Differential Equation (t))} \rightarrow \text{Circuit Differential Equation (s)}$$

Now this is the case in the simplest case but again the Laplace Integral Transform operator,

$\widehat{\text{Laplace}}()$ can be replaced with other general integral transform operators. In this case the voltage can be made a function of the current but it is crucial to recognize for the full image that we have to take the Laplace transform of both the circuit differential equation and the physics differential equation. In this case there are 2 control variables, not only is the voltage a function of time but it is a function of the distance of the ball, so this requires the introduction of a 3d Laplace transformation because the voltage on pin #1 = $V_{\#1} = V_{\#1}(x, t)$. So the Laplace transformation should be: $\widehat{\text{Laplace}}(V_{\#1}(x, t)) = V_{\#1}(\sigma, s)$. So this will give us a new function in the domain (σ, s) where from the geometries of the (σ, s) plot which might be simpler to analyze is related to the geometries of the original coordinates. This shows how then the transfer function can be formed from the 3d voltage function as well as the Nyquist plots. In summary the integral transforms operating on the differential equations transform the geometries into things which are able to be handled in some cases and which gives a full set of information about the circuit phenomena. Viewing it through this perspective it can be understood how the coil geometries essentially produce the variations in the differential equation for the circuit. Such variations in the force functions provide the basis for the application of differential geometry to control systems.

Generalizing this notion to all types of differential equations one might determine quantities such as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Integral Transform(Einstein Differential Equation (t))} \\ \rightarrow \text{Einstein Differential Equation (s)} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 67)}$$

If we define a Newtonian differential equation as:

$$\left(m \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} \right) = \frac{k}{(a^2 + y^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} - mg \right) \quad \text{Eq 68)}$$

Then we can take the Laplace transformation:

$$\widehat{\text{Laplace}} \left(m \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dt^2} \right) = \frac{k}{(a^2 + y^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} - mg \right) \rightarrow \left(ms^2 y(s) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{k}{(a^2 + y^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} e^{-sy} dy - \frac{mg}{s} \right) \quad \text{Eq 69)}$$

In some cases the Laplace transform cannot be solved for analytically but in these cases it can be done by numerical computation of the integral. This is a lemma which must be proved rigorously but which we will use anyways that:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{k}{(a^2 + y^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} e^{-sy} dy = f(s)y(s) \quad \text{Eq 70}$$

Writing the newton force law similar to how the Kirchhoff law is written so that we include the extra term in the equation for forces with:

$$F(s) = \left(ms^2 + f(s) - \frac{mg}{s} \right) y(s) \quad \text{Eq 71}$$

And then we can define the transfer function by diving both sides by $F(s)$ and $T(s) = y(s)/F(s)$ so that we obtain

$$T(s) = \frac{1}{\left(ms^2 + f(s) - \frac{mg}{s} \right)} \quad \text{Eq 72}$$

It appears that some law needs to be made that relates the physics transfer function to the Newtonian transfer function as this relates the phenomena in the system. Another question I have is, is there an energy transfer function and what is the Laplace and integral transforms of the Lagrangian functions?

Data Acquisition

Data acquisition refers to the process of collecting and gathering information from various sources for further analysis or monitoring. It involves the conversion of physical parameters, signals, or measurements into digital data that can be processed by a computer.

Several types of data acquisition systems exist, each tailored to specific applications. Common categories include sensor based acquisition and data acquisition for control systems.

Sensors can be connected to circuits and the values can be read in terms of voltages which is related to other quantities such as temperature. This is an example for data acquisition for temperature from Arduino but there are other types of sensors. In this experiment we used the Arduino as an oscilloscope as well as purchased an oscilloscope and displayed the sensor data from the circuit sensors. One such example is the position data from a time of flight sensor. This gives the position of the ball but if an ai program were to analyze this situation we would need other inputs such as camera data to tell the computer what the ball is made out of so that the correct equations of motion can be obtained by observation. It is clear that different sensors used whether it be the time of flight sensor or the Hall Effect sensor essentially determine the types of algorithms that are implemented since each sensor gives the data in a different data type. The code however can be interpreted as the same with a converter between data types. Therefore it takes different combinations of sensors and data types, not a singular data type for an agi to generate the physics of the system as well as determine appropriate apparatus design as well as circuit design.

There are also data acquisition technologies such as LabVIEW and Matlab. Not only can the Arduino be used as a real time data acquisition device but it leads to other general micro and controllers which can be modeled similarly and can handle larger loads and more inputs for data acquisition. Some such technologies are plcs and industrial controllers.

OrCAD, Pspice, Matlab, and using the Arduino as oscilloscope are other data acquisition technologies. After the open loop circuit which describes the basic circuit as was described in the previous section is constructed and simulated, then the control loop can be added to make this a closed loop system. The control loop in this situation consisted of the Time of Flight position sensor -the steps to connect and test it on the Arduino to be

completed are available on the Adafruit website, and the sensor is connected to the Arduino which in turn is connected to the breadboard. The time of flight code is within the examples of the Arduino code files, once it has been set up.

I also had to download some drivers for the Arduino in addition to running some test code to ensure that it worked properly. The Arduino website and examples dropdown within the program have many different examples and test code which is where I first tested that the Arduino oscilloscope functions as there is a built in oscilloscope with the serial monitor underneath the tools section.

Using the various different sensors within the kit you can use the Arduino for almost any data acquisition setup. This is also the case with raspberry pi as well as other microcontrollers. Arduino also sells other microcontrollers such as Arduino Nano.

Stability Conditions of the Riemann Zeta Function and the Implications for the Riemann Hypothesis

We would define the Nyquist plot as $Nyquist\ plot = (|U(x, y)|, |V(x, y)|)$

This requires separating the real part and imaginary parts of the zeta function.

$$\zeta(x + iy) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{t^{x-1} t^{iy} dt}{e^t - 1}; \tag{Eq 73}$$

$$\Gamma(s) = \int_0^{\infty} t^{s-1} e^{-t} dt \tag{Eq 74}$$

Then using the fact that $t^{iy} = e^{iy \ln(t)}$ this integral can be converted into

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \left(\int_0^{\infty} \frac{t^{x-1} \cos(y \ln(t)) dt}{e^t - 1} + i \int_0^{\infty} \frac{t^{x-1} \sin(y \ln(t)) dt}{e^t - 1} \right) \tag{Eq 75}$$

For use in a few lines define:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{t^{x-1} \cos(y \ln(t)) dt}{e^t - 1} = U \tag{Eq 75}$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{t^{x-1} \sin(y \ln(t)) dt}{e^t - 1} = V \tag{Eq 76}$$

Then to separate this function into the real and imaginary parts the gamma function and its reciprocal must be evaluated in terms of a real and imaginary part which is multiplied into the integral on the RHS of the equation above.

$$Re(\Gamma(s)) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{t^{x-1} \cos(t \ln(t)) dt}{e^t} = U_{\Gamma}; \tag{Eq 77}$$

$$Im(\Gamma(s)) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{t^{x-1} \sin(t \ln(t)) dt}{e^t} = V_{\Gamma}; \tag{Eq 78}$$

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} = \frac{1}{U_{\Gamma} + iV_{\Gamma}} = \frac{1}{U_{\Gamma} + iV_{\Gamma}} \left(\frac{U_{\Gamma} - iV_{\Gamma}}{U_{\Gamma} - iV_{\Gamma}} \right) = \frac{U_{\Gamma} - iV_{\Gamma}}{U_{\Gamma}^2 - V_{\Gamma}^2} \tag{Eq 79}$$

$$\therefore \zeta(s) = \frac{U_\Gamma - iV_\Gamma}{U_\Gamma^2 - V_\Gamma^2} (U + iV) = \frac{U_\Gamma U - V_\Gamma V}{U_\Gamma^2 - V_\Gamma^2} + \frac{i(-V_\Gamma U + U_\Gamma V)}{U_\Gamma^2 - V_\Gamma^2} \quad \text{Eq 80}$$

And finally this implies that

$$\text{Re}(\zeta(s)) = \frac{U_\Gamma U - V_\Gamma V}{U_\Gamma^2 - V_\Gamma^2} \quad \text{Eq 81}$$

And

$$\text{Im}(\zeta(s)) = \frac{(-V_\Gamma U + U_\Gamma V)}{U_\Gamma^2 - V_\Gamma^2} \quad \text{Eq 82}$$

Therefore the Nyquist plot is defined as:

$$\text{Nyquist} = \left(\text{Re}(\zeta(s)), \text{Im}(\zeta(s)) \right) = \left(\frac{U_\Gamma U - V_\Gamma V}{U_\Gamma^2 - V_\Gamma^2}, \frac{(-V_\Gamma U + U_\Gamma V)}{U_\Gamma^2 - V_\Gamma^2} \right) \quad \text{Eq 83}$$

Then we have a phasor representation of the zeta function:

$$\zeta(s) = \begin{pmatrix} \text{Re}(\zeta(s)) \\ \text{Im}(\zeta(s)) \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 84}$$

Each axis exhibits stability conditions when seeking overall system stability. By employing the 3D Laplace transform on the 3D Newton equation, we gain the capability to determine the 3D transfer function for the circuit. The circuit's dimensions are primarily influenced by the number of control axes. Extracting the real and imaginary parts of the 3D transfer function for each dimension results in a total of six parts. While a 6D plot is possible, for simplicity, the stability analysis is conducted through a 3D Nyquist plot. This plot is a function of both the real and imaginary parts, effectively condensing the comprehensive view of the circuit's behavior in the complex plane into a single surface plot.

The 4D Nyquist plot is formally defined as $(\text{Real}(T(x, y, z, t)), \text{Im}(T(x, y, z, t)))$.

Figure 39 [*39]: Generalizing the 1d Model.

Now that we have the full model for the control of one of these coils in 3 space, we can generalize this to implement different control functions such as moving the ball around a 4d path from an orientation such as Figure 38.

This, as well as other coil orientations lead to various magnetic field control technologies. Generalizing these principles can lead to developing the new circuits, determining the new algorithms, equations, control functions, sensors and apparatus etc could be used for many different technologies which are already known to exist such as described within this paper. If particles are envisioned as tiny dipoles, the situation is similar if we were to trap particles or groups of particles within a device built by many surrounding electromagnets around the particles, theoretically we could control aspects of the interactions and some parts of the particle trajectory by controlling the particles with the magnetic field. This can be accomplished with arrays of nanoelectromagnetic coils. This is essentially the basis for magnetic nanoparticle and microparticle control. The magnetic field for the nanocoil needs solved for and this would be done according to the biot savart law for the nanocurrents within the nanocoil. The magnetic fields from the nanocoils would in theory be able to be used to control nano particles.

If we use 5 coils as pictured within the above image, then we have 5 main components of the magnetic field again here ignoring fringing but this might have to be considered in the more general cases. We can define the total B field as:

$$\vec{B} = \sum_{i=1}^5 \vec{B}_i \quad \text{Eq 85)}$$

The general newton equation must consider the torque on the ball which is a function of time because then the ball will have an angular momentum that is a function of the field.

The newton equation for the ball is:

$$m \frac{d^2 \vec{r}}{dt^2} = (\vec{m} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \sum_{i=1}^5 \vec{B}_i - mg \hat{y} \quad \text{Eq 86)}$$

The Spin equation for the ball is:

$$\frac{d\vec{L}}{dt} = \vec{r} \times \vec{F} = \vec{r} \times ((\vec{m} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \vec{B}) = \vec{r} \times \left((\vec{m} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \sum_{i=1}^5 \vec{B}_i \right) \quad \text{Eq 87)}$$

$$\vec{B}_1 = \hat{y} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + x_1^2 + (y - y_1)^2 + z_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dy \quad \text{Eq 88)}$$

$$\vec{B}_2 = \hat{x} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + (x - x_1)^2 + (y_1)^2 + z_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dx \quad \text{Eq 89)}$$

$$\vec{B}_3 = \hat{x} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + (x + x_1)^2 + (y_1)^2 + z_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dx \quad \text{Eq 90)}$$

$$\vec{B}_4 = \hat{z} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + x_1^2 + (y_1)^2 + (z - z_1)^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dz \quad \text{Eq 91)}$$

$$\vec{B}_5 = \hat{z} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + x_1^2 + (y_1)^2 + (z + z_1)^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dz \quad \text{Eq 92)}$$

So this makes the total magnetic field,

$$\vec{B} = \begin{pmatrix} \hat{x} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + (x - x_1)^2 + (y_1)^2 + z_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dx - \hat{x} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + (x + x_1)^2 + (y_1)^2 + z_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dx \\ \hat{y} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + x_1^2 + (y - y_1)^2 + z_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dy \\ \hat{z} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + x_1^2 + (y_1)^2 + (z - z_1)^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dz - \hat{z} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + x_1^2 + (y_1)^2 + (z + z_1)^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dz \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 93)}$$

$$m \frac{d^2 \vec{r}}{dt^2} = (\vec{m} \cdot \vec{\nabla}) \begin{pmatrix} \hat{x} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + (x - x_1)^2 + (y_1)^2 + z_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dx - \hat{x} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + (x + x_1)^2 + (y_1)^2 + z_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dx \\ \hat{y} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + x_1^2 + (y - y_1)^2 + z_1^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dy \\ \hat{z} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + x_1^2 + (y_1)^2 + (z - z_1)^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dz - \hat{z} \int \frac{\mu_0 i N}{2} \left(\frac{R^2}{(R^2 + x_1^2 + (y_1)^2 + (z + z_1)^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) dz \end{pmatrix} - mg \hat{y} \quad \text{Eq 94)}$$

This coupled nonlinear differential equation contains all the information for the system. This equation gives the stability conditions by setting $\frac{d^2\vec{r}}{dt^2} = 0$. The circuit variable implementation is identically defined for each axis.

This apparatus is easily generalized by the model for the 1d case. And by changing the algorithms in the 1d case we can control the position function of the ball to any trajectory in 1d space and time by changing the algorithms used and instead of using the stability function for the set point, setting the desired function of choice. We need 4 more electromagnets to control the position of the magnets in 3 space. The ball moves in 3 space but it moves in time so a space-time can be given for the ball as well as the Lagrangian and the related functions. We can plot the trajectory of the ball in space time if we chose to as well.

The circuit needs 4 more transistors, resistors, and diodes as well as wires for each. Each coil also needs two Hall Effect sensors, giving us 10 sensors. Then we would need to connect these to the power sources. Note that the bread board could easily support 6 different power sources if they are needed but it appears on first inspection that the same voltage source could be shared at the one node of each electro magnet and the other end of each coil gets connected to a different digital pin.

An example of such a robot is having the ball stably levitate or doing some motion in the small scale while then we either move the coils relative to the ball or move the apparatus relative to the ball. Then we would need to add extra force terms. The extra force terms would be balance by the robot which is making this motion. Another such variation of this experiment includes making the ball a magnetic robot which we can control other motions or shoot lasers from the ball as it moves through a space without touching anything.

Declarations

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Figure References

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